

**Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration
in European rural areas**

D1.2 Stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests

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Executive Summary

The main objective of BioRural is to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network under which related stakeholders could cooperate to promote currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas, giving increased value in such remote areas. BioRural is going to develop a transition framework towards a sustainable, regenerative, inclusive and just circular Bioeconomy across all Europe at a local and regional scale. One of the strategic objectives of BioRural is to identify factors affecting the adoption of innovation and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas along five Bioeconomy themes (food and agriculture, forestry and natural habitats, aquatic systems, bioenergy and biomaterials). Based on a structured survey with bio-based solutions' experts (46 experts were interviewed) and end-users' (422 end-users were interviewed), the project assesses experts' and end-users' needs and interests, as well as identifies and characterises the adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas..

D1.2. includes the methodology for innovation processes' analyses and the results of the end-users' survey of bio-based solutions, as well as experts in all five bioeconomy fields describing the factors influencing adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas. The methodological framework of the surveys includes the description of the survey target population, sampling units, and sample size by geographical location for both end-users' and experts' surveys, as well as the design of sample structure, the survey limitations, a clear description of the survey data collection process, the approach of data analysis and the design of both questionnaires. Also, the methodology provided BioRural partners with recommendations and advice on survey organising in their countries. Moreover, the report introduces the end-users' and experts' survey results and their interpretations, complementarities, similarities, and differences in their approaches, as well as the differences in the RBP regions. The surveys were conducted in each partner country and then summarised to present the status and/or approach of each RBP region (North-West RPB, South-West RBP, North-East RBP, South-East RBP). The survey data has been analysed and interpreted considering the statistically significant differences between the answers. Statistical significance helped to ensure that the observed differences in survey responses were not due to random chance.

The main conclusions of the survey results are summarised and presented in the following structure:

- **The adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas.** End-users work with stakeholders to make bio-based solutions more sustainable (renewable, inclusive, circular). More than half of them do this with customers, suppliers, researchers and outside advisors. According to the surveyed experts, small-scale bio-based solutions can be more successfully implemented when active and significant involvement of different type stakeholders exists, and especially if in the beginning of the process agricultural or scientific advisors are involved.
- **Incentives to become adopters of bio-based solutions.** Economic benefit and enhanced product performance and/or functionalities are the main incentives to become adopters of innovative bio-based solutions. According to the experts surveyed, promoting circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas requires a multi-faceted approach that goes beyond economic incentives and addresses the needs of social incentives such as stronger collaborations, knowledge share, demonstrations and peer-to-peer learning.
- **Barriers for adoption of bio-based solutions.** According to nearly two-thirds of end-users surveyed, a lack of financial capital is one of the main barriers to adopting innovative bio-based solutions. Furthermore, the experts have stressed that the barriers vary depending on the specific context for the region, but here are some common challenges that adopters and non-adopters are facing. Those barriers are lack of skills and qualified personnel, insufficient and/or complex regulations, limited funding, etc.
- **Driving factors for adoption of bio-based solutions.** According to the opinion of the surveyed end-users, the main driving factors for adoption of innovative bio-based solutions are long-term economic benefits

and supplier/customer demand. Surveyed experts have agreed that the demand for bio-based solutions (products and services) is playing a key role in deciding on the adoption of bio-based solutions.

- **Ideas and interests to adopt bio-based solutions.** Almost four out of five surveyed end-users agree that coverage of customers' needs for bio-based solutions, use for locally sourced feedstocks and etc. are the specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution. The experts' survey results have highlighted the fact that choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in the region varies based on the specific context, and industry of the country, but here are some key factors to consider which have no significant differences across the RBPs.
- **Accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.** Most of the surveyed end-users think that economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries, incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based products and bioenergy, and incentives for producers to adopt bio-based solutions are the accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. Surveyed experts agree that in a short time the dissemination of information about legal instruments, support schemes, technologies and product use could be the key factors for the acceleration of small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.

In general, the results of the end-users' survey show that socio-demographic and business structural characteristics play an important role in their responses.

The survey results explored the current perceptions, challenges, and opportunities within these domains, to shape the future of sustainable practices in various bioeconomy areas. Therefore, the recommendations were prepared which are crucial for guiding stakeholders toward more sustainable practices and fostering bio-based innovation in all five bioeconomy themes. The ultimate significance of these recommendations lies in their potential to drive sustainable growth and circular bioeconomy in different European regions. To ensure a comprehensive approach to circular bioeconomy development, the recommendations were grouped into the following categories: Awareness campaigns and training, Policy regulation and Support, Community Engagement and Collaboration, Market Access and Promotion, and Research and Development. The prepared recommendations are the summary outcomes of the end-users' and experts' survey results, their interpretations, and insights. More specific recommendations were prepared after the in-depth discussions with end-users and experts to address the specific country's needs and specific practices in bioeconomy area.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1
CBE	– Circular bioeconomy
CE	– Circular economy
CH4	– Methane
CHP	– Combined Heat and Power
CO ₂	– Carbon dioxide
EU	– European Union
NGOs	– Non-governmental organization
R&D	– Research and development.
RBP	– Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
RES	– Renewable energy sources
SME	– Small and medium-sized enterprise (SMEs)

Bio-based processes means switching to using biological resources and biological processing methods in a sustainable way (BioRural definition).

Bio-based product refers to products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees, algae or animals (the biomass can have undergone physical, chemical, biological treatment, etc.), excluding materials embedded in geological formations and/or fossilised [5].

Bio-based solutions are innovative technologies and practices based on circularity that produce or utilise biomass sustainably as compared to mainstream practices that produce or utilise biomass without significant innovations or sustainable outputs (BioRural definition).

Bioeconomy refers to all systems that are dependent on biological resources (biomass, animals, plants, organisms), their functions and principles. It includes land and marine ecosystems; primary production sectors (agriculture,

forestry, fisheries and aquaculture) and all economic and industrial sectors using biological resources to produce food, feed, biobased products, energy and services [1].

Bioenergy is a source of energy from the organic material that makes up plants, known as biomass [2].

Biotechnology is the application of science and technology to living organisms, as well as parts, products, and models thereof, to alter living or non-living materials for the production of knowledge, goods and services (BioRural definition).

Circular Bioeconomy (CBE) is the application of the circular economy concept/principles to biological resources, products, and materials [3].

Circular economy (CE) is an economy where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste minimised [3].

End-users are individuals or small-medium sized organisations whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes, mainly operating in rural areas, and limited to the primary and secondary sectors (limited to the factory gate). Some examples include bio-based raw material producers (farmers, fishermen/women, foresters), small scale bio-based industries, biorefineries and bioenergy producers (BioRural definition).

Small-medium sized organisations are the category of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Micro-enterprises are defined as enterprises that employ fewer than 10 persons and whose annual turnover or annual balance sheet total does not exceed EUR 2 million. Small enterprises are defined as enterprises that employ fewer than 50 persons and whose annual turnover or annual balance sheet total does not exceed EUR 10 million. Medium-sized enterprises are defined as enterprises that employ fewer than 250 persons and either have an annual turnover that does not exceed EUR 50 million, or an annual balance sheet not exceeding EUR 43 million. [4]

Small-scale solutions are solutions of individuals and organisations that are small and limited in extent (BioRural definition).

1 Introduction

BioRural's main objective is to establish a Pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network, within which related stakeholders will cooperate to promote currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas, thereby enhancing their value in these remote areas. This framework aims to bridge the gap between available novel high-end bio-based solutions and the daily lives of rural European citizens by assessing the current state of the European rural bioeconomy, capturing grassroots-level needs and ideas, promoting an effective exchange of knowledge and information, and exploring the business opportunities for regional development through the integration of bio-based solutions in rural Europe.

This report presents the survey results from both end-users of bio-based solutions and experts across all five bioeconomy fields. The survey aims to identify the factors that affect innovation of adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The analysis and synthesis of the survey results provided valuable insights into the specific needs, preferences, challenges, and experiences faced by end-users, encompassing both adopters and non-adopters in rural areas, helping to identify their needs, ideas, driving factors, and barriers to adopting innovative bio-based solutions. This information is crucial for tailoring bio-based solutions to effectively address the challenges related to circular bioeconomy in rural areas.

The report structure consists of an introduction and brief overview of the methodology which has been verified through active discussions with all consortium partners. The methodological framework for the surveys includes the description of the survey target population, sampling units, and sample sizes categorised by geographical location for both end-users and experts, as well as the design of the sample structure, the survey's limitations, a clear description of the data collection process, the approach of data analysis and the design of both questionnaires. Furthermore, the methodology provided BioRural partners with recommendations and guidance for organising surveys in their respective countries.

Moreover, the report introduces the results of both end-users' and experts' surveys and their interpretations, complementarities, similarities, and differences in their approaches, as well as the differences in the RBP regions. The surveys were conducted in each partner country and then summarised to present the status and/or approach of each RBP region (North-West RPB, South-West RPB, North-East RPB, South-East RPB).

The survey data has been analysed and interpreted considering statistically significant differences among the responses. Statistical significance helped to ensure that the observed variations in survey responses occur not by random chance. Consequently, it provides a level of confidence in the findings, enhancing their reliability and credibility. Moreover, this approach is essential for ensuring the accuracy, validity, and utility of the survey results, thereby providing solid conclusions and a foundation for data-driven recommendations.

The surveys have yielded conclusions and recommendations as their summarising outcome. These recommendations are essential for a wide array of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, both newcomers and established leaders in the agro-industry, as well as those who have adopted bio-based solutions and those who haven't, alongside environmental advocates. The recommendations, as presented in this report are based on a comprehensive analysis of survey responses, merging the practical insights of end-users with the strategic insights of experts. These recommendations have been structured into different categories and the ultimate significance of provided recommendations lies in their potential to drive sustainable growth and promote the circular bioeconomy across different European regions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Methodological framework for the survey

Target population

The project focuses on small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas across five bioeconomy overlapping thematic areas: food/agriculture, forestry/natural habitats, and water systems, which emphasise primary production systems; bioenergy and biomaterials/ bio-based products which are secondary processing systems. Thus, we hypothesised that both the *kind* and the *scale of bioeconomy activity* of individuals and business organisations operating in rural areas **are the key criteria to characterise the target population in the survey**.

In the project, the target population is defined as end-users. It is individuals or small-medium-sized organisations whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes, mainly operate in rural areas, and are limited to the primary and secondary sectors (limited to the factory gate). Furthermore, the experts of Bioeconomy and bio-based solutions are going to be involved in this survey. Experts are considered those professionals who have a high level of expertise (education or practical work) in one or more of Bioeconomy themes.

RBP's countries present very different patterns of their bioeconomic activities. Although, some sectors like the manufacture of food, beverages and tobacco, and agriculture are widely dominating in most RBP's countries. Latvia, Germany, and Slovenia are countries where the share of agriculture in the total bioeconomy turnover is one of the smallest. In Latvia, the manufacture of food, beverages, and tobacco was a larger bioeconomy turnover generator than agriculture. In Germany, agriculture contributed to 12% of Germany's bioeconomy turnover, while in Slovenia agriculture generated 17.4% of the overall bioeconomy turnover and it was almost the same as in the manufacture of wood products and furniture (Fig. 1). The agriculture, forestry, and water systems (fishing and aquaculture) are mainly located in rural areas, while the food and bioprocessing industries (bioenergy, biomaterials, and bio-products) are spread between rural, peripheral, and urban areas, showing the direct relationship between rural and urban communities.

Source: composition based on Data portal of agro-economics Modelling (DataM) of the European Commission, own calculations for North Macedonia

Figure 1: Turnover in the bioeconomy sectors of activity in the country by RBP, in percentage, 2019

2.2 Methodology of end-users' survey

2.2.1 Survey target

Target population

According to the project, the target population of the survey is end-users, which in this project means individuals or small-medium-sized organisations whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes, mainly operate in rural areas, and are limited to the primary and secondary sectors (limited to the factory gate).

The aim of the survey

The survey of end-users aims to assess the needs, interests, and innovation processes of the main rural bioeconomy stakeholders and the factors affecting the adoption of bio-based solutions.

Sampling unit

An end-user refers to an individual or small-medium size organisation whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes, mainly operating in rural areas, and limited to the primary and secondary sectors (limited to the factory gate). For example, end-users are bio-based raw material producers such as farmers, fishermen/women, and foresters, small-medium scale bio-based industries, biorefineries, and bioenergy producers.

Sample size by geographical location

According to the project, the total sample of the survey is at least 400 end-users, where the confidence level is 95% and $p=0.05$. Interviews with >100 end-users from the pre-classified groups are going to be conducted by each Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platform (RBP) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Sample size of end-users by RBP and countries' location

Sampling frame by countries

The sampling frame prepared individually for every country (see Annex I).

The design of sample structure

The sample of end-users is framed by:

- 1. Dividing five Bioeconomy themes into seven subsectors in line with the bioeconomic structure of each country** (see Annex I):
 - Food/agriculture, including both sectors, such as the manufacture of food, beverage, tobacco, and agriculture.
 - Forestry/natural habitats, including forestry and logging, and the manufacture of wood products and furniture.
 - Water systems, i.e., fishery, aquaculture, aquatic.
 - Biomaterials/bio-based products, including the manufacture of bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, etc.
 - Bioenergy, including the bio-based electricity sector, biogas sector, etc.
- 2. Determining the number of end-users by bioeconomy subsector in line with their proportion in the bioeconomy structure** (see Annex I):
 - *first*, the approximate sample size of end-users is distributed by bioeconomy sectors proportionally to its %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover;
 - *second*, the corrections of the sample size of end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas, bearing in mind that the primary production sectors are mainly located in rural areas.
 - *third*, redistribution of the end-user's sample size between bioeconomy sectors can also be done by project partners (*if needed*) who know the actual state of the rural bioeconomy and its structure in their own country. The revision of suggested numbers of end-users is recommended.
- 3. The approximate percentage distribution of end-users by the legal form applies in the sampling frame in line with the national statistics related to farm structure and business demography characteristics in bioeconomy sectors at the country level.** Eurostat legal forms classification and definition for agricultural holdings and enterprises by size apply to the sampling frame for the survey (see Annex I).
- 4. The approximate percentage distribution of end-users by size of economic activities applies in the sampling frame in line with the national statistics related to farm structure and business demography characteristics in bioeconomy sectors at the country level.** The European Commission's SME definition and classification by staff headcount criteria apply to the sampling frame for the survey (see Annex I).
- 5. The approximate percentage distribution of end-users by the kind of production practices (i.e., primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks, processing of these materials into value-added products and the processing of biowaste into value-added products) and its combinations which are included in the end-users sampling structure** (see Annex I). It is recommended to keep the approximate 50/50 percentage distribution of interviewing adopters and non-adopters.
- 6. The sampling frame for regions indicates that end-users that are going to be selected from rural areas should cover the four categories of NUTS-3 regions:** "predominantly rural regions, close to a city" and "predominantly rural, remote regions", as well as "intermediate regions, close to a city" and "intermediate remote regions" (see Data collection section).

The approximate sample data aggregated by BRP region and by countries are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

<i>Summarised data for the whole project and for the RBPs</i>	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/ bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, biogas, etc.	
Total in the whole project								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	176-191	100-115	42-58	15-29	2-16	68-84	9-23	412-516
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	87-102	153-168	32-47	45-60	27-42	38-51	30-46	412-516
	240-270		77-107		27-42	38-51	30-46	412-516
Total in North-West RBP								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	55-60	20-24	5-9	1-5	0-4	19-23	3-7	104-132
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	27-31	34-38	5-9	9-13	8-12	11-15	10-14	104-132
	61-69		14-22		8-12	11-15	10-14	104-132
Total in South-West RBP								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	48-52	19-22	8-12	1-4	1-4	23-27	2-5	102-126
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	25-29	36-39	6-10	7-11	7-11	13-15	8-11	102-126
	61-68		13-21		7-11	13-15	8-11	102-126
Total in North-East RBP								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	38-41	23-26	21-25	9-12	0-3	9-13	3-6	102-126
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	18-21	33-37	14-17	19-22	6-9	5-8	7-12	102-126
	51-58		33-39		6-9	5-8	7-12	102-126
Total in South-East RBP								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	34-38	39-43	8-12	4-8	1-5	17-21	1-5	104-132
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	17-21	50-54	7-11	10-14	6-10	9-13	5-9	104-132
	67-75		17-25		6-10	9-13	5-9	104-132

Table 1: Summarized sample data by the RBPs

Corrected approximate number* of end-users' survey	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/ bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, biogas, etc.	
<i>North-West RBP</i>								
Netherlands	7-8	10-11	1-2	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
France	7-8	9-10	1-2	3-4	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
Germany	7-8	6-7	2-3	2-3	2-3	4-5	3-4	26-33
Denmark	6-7	9-10	1-2	2-3	2-3	3-4	3-4	26-33
<i>South-West RBP</i>								
Spain	10-12	14-15	1-2	2-3	2-3	3-4	2-3	34-42
Portugal	7-8	11-12	3-4	3-5	3-5	4-5	3-4	34-42
Italy	8-9	11-12	2-4	2-3	2-3	6-7	3-4	34-42
<i>North-East RBP</i>								
Latvia	3-4	8-9	7-8	11-12	2-3	1-2	2-4	34-42
Lithuania	6-7	13-15	4-5	4-5	2-3	2-3	3-4	34-42
Poland	9-10	12-13	3-4	4-5	2-3	2-3	2-4	34-42
<i>South-East RBP</i>								
Greece	6-7	12-13	1-2	1-2	3-4	1-2	2-3	26-33
Slovenia	4-5	8-9	3-4	5-6	1-2	4-5	1-2	26-33
North Macedonia	3-4	18-19	1-2	2-3	0-1	2-4	0-1	26-33
Romania	4-5	12-13	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
Total	87-102	153-168	32-47	45-60	27-42	38-51	30-46	412-516
	240-270		77-107		27-42	38-51	30-46	412-516

Table 2: Summarised sample data by countries

Data collection

The survey is going to be conducted by project partners from each country. Contact with respondents shall be established through the project partner of each country, based on the sampling guide presented below, using their established networks with end-users (individuals or small-medium-sized organisations) in their countries.

To achieve the best possible distribution, the aim is to select individuals or small-medium-sized organisations located in various rural areas of regions that are remote or located close to city centres. In this term, the urban-rural typology including remoteness, developed by the European Commission at the level of the NUTS-3 region, is going to be used. End-users for the survey are going to be selected from four categories of NUTS-3 such as the “predominantly rural regions, close to a city” and “predominantly rural, remote regions”, as well as “intermediate regions, close to a city” and “intermediate remote regions”, as equally as possible.

The Nomenclature of territorial units (abbreviated NTES) of the Republic of North Macedonia is harmonised with the Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (abbreviated NUTS) of the European Union. At NTES level 3 (corresponds to NUTS 3), there are 8 statistical regions, i.e. Polog region, Southwest region, Pelagonia region, Vardar region, Skopje region, Northeast region, East region, and Southeast region. However, urban-rural typology of NUTS 3 regions including remoteness does not apply to the Republic of North Macedonia. For this reason, end-users in rural areas are surveyed regardless of remoteness in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Project partners are going to conduct interviews (either via telephone or in person) with end-users in each study country. Each of the project partner-interviewers shall be introduced to their role (are going to know their role) in the survey. It is important that the interviewers stay neutral since their presence in the survey process should not

have any effect on the responses given to questionnaire items. Interviewers are going to be introduced to the questionnaire, survey objectives and the survey procedures (including anonymity, etc.).

The survey shall be conducted from mid-February to early May of 2023. The survey is to be conducted in electronic form, according to each interviewer's needs, and responses are going to be transferred to a master excel file via the online form in the survey platform EUSurvey (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BIORURAL>). Only the project partners are to be allowed to access the online form. Each end-user interviewed is going to be provided with a consent letter ensuring the anonymity of the collected data and their agreement to participate.

Data analysis

The survey data is going to be entered into the online survey platform "EUSurvey" Form to streamline data management. The data is going to be downloaded from the Form as a spreadsheet and used for further analysis with IBM SPSS Statistics. The survey results from each partner country are going to be analysed summarising the survey result to 4 regional RBPs and as a whole for the whole EU. The data sets are going to be analysed using the chi-square test to test for differences between the groups of end-users according to regional RBPs, bioeconomy themes, localisation (remoteness) of the end-users regions, and socio-demographic and business structural characteristics.

2.2.2 Design of a questionnaire for end-user survey

The questionnaire for end-users (adopters and non-adopters) is structured by categorising the questions into three groups:

1. Group of questions aiming at collecting general information about the end-users of bio-based solutions, focusing on their sociodemographic and social characteristics, business structure, and the specific bio-economy theme in which they are operating. Some of these questions are specifically addressed to both adopters and non-adopters, while others apply to both types of end-users.
2. Group of questions aiming at identifying barriers and driving factors for adopting bio-based solutions. This group of questions applies to both adopters and non-adopters.
3. Group of questions aiming at identifying end-users' needs, ideas, and interests regarding the adoption of bio-based solutions. This group of questions applies to both adopters and non-adopters.

The questionnaire for end-users has been prepared following these steps:

1. Questionnaires have been prepared by the WP lead partner (Vytauto, VDU) and validated by the project partners. Partners' comments and recommendations regarding the survey structure and content were integrated into the final version of the questionnaire (see Annex II).
2. The appropriateness of the questionnaire was pre-tested with end-users in February 2023 in each partner country. Notes were taken on sensitive, unclear, or unnecessary questions, as well as on survey structure and length. These notes were considered and used to refine the questionnaire.
3. The final questionnaire has been integrated into the online survey platform EUSurvey (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BIORURAL>). While the survey is initially in English, most of the end-users operate at the local or regional level, and their English language skills may be limited. Therefore, it is recommended to either translate the questionnaires into partners' national languages or conduct the survey in the local language. However, the survey results should be submitted in English to the online survey platform mentioned above.

2.3 Methodology of expert's survey

2.3.1 Survey target

The aim of the survey

The survey of experts aims to assess the needs, interests, and innovation processes of the main rural bioeconomy stakeholders, as well as the factors affecting the adoption of bio-based solutions.

Sampling unit

An 'expert' in this context refers to an individual with a high level of expertise in one or more of five bioeconomy themes. These experts can provide insights into the needs, interests, innovation processes, capacities, barriers, and driving factors necessary for the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

Sample size by geographical location

According to the project's guidelines, the total sample size for the survey consists of a minimum of 40 experts. Interviews with at least 3 experts from the pre-classified groups have been conducted by each country:

Figure 3: Sample size of experts by RBP and countries' locations

Sample structure

Experts are invited to perform as providers/developers of bio-based solutions, as well as professors/researchers, policymakers, advisors/innovation brokers, and others with a high level of expertise. This expertise is demonstrated through qualifications and/or practical experience in at least one, preferably all, of the bioeconomy themes.

Data collection

The survey will be conducted by project partners in each participating country. Contact with respondents will be established through the project partner in each country, based on the sampling guide presented below, using their established networks with end-users (individuals or small-medium-sized organisations) in their countries.

Project partners will conduct telephone or in-person interviews with end-users in each study country. Each project partner-interviewer will be introduced to their role in the survey and will stay neutral since their presence in the

survey process should not have any effect on the responses given to questionnaire items. Interviewers will be introduced to the questionnaire.

The survey will take place from mid-February to early May 2023 and will be administered in electronic form, according to each interviewer's preferences. Responses will be transferred to a master Excel file via the online form on a survey platform EUSurvey (https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BIORURAL_EXPERT) Only project partners will be allowed access to the online form. Each expert interviewed will be provided with a consent letter guaranteeing the anonymity of collected data and their agreement to participate.

Data analysis

The survey data will be entered into the online survey platform 'EUSurvey'. Data will be downloaded from the form as a spreadsheet and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics. The survey results from each partner country will be summarized to create an overview of the survey results for the four regional RBPs.

The results of expert interviews will be merged, compared, and analysed alongside end-users' survey results. This combined analysis will help identify the correlations between responses, interpret the survey results and formulate the conclusions and recommendations for improved adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

2.3.2 Design of a questionnaire for experts

The questionnaire for experts is designed by categorising questions into three groups:

1. A group of questions aimed at collecting **general information** about the experts' sociodemographic characteristics and the sector they are representing.
2. A group of questions addressing the experts' opinions on **the capacity to adopt bio-based solutions** in rural areas.
3. A group of questions addressing experts' opinions on **the needs, ideas, and interests** to speed up the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The questionnaire for experts was prepared following these steps:

1. The questionnaire was initially prepared by the WP lead partner (Vytauto, VDU) and validated by project partners. Partners' comments and recommendations regarding the survey structure and content were integrated into the final version of the questionnaire (see Annex III).
2. The questionnaire's appropriateness was pre-tested with experts in February 2023 in each partner country. Notes on sensitive, unclear, and/or unnecessary questions, survey structure, and length were considered and used to finalise the questionnaire.
3. The final questionnaire has been integrated into the online survey platform EUSurvey (https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BIORURAL_EXPERT).
4. The survey language is English. Depending on the needs, it is recommended to provide a translated version of the questionnaire for experts or conduct the survey in the local language. Nevertheless, the survey results should be submitted in English to the online survey platform mentioned above.

2.4 Survey preparatory workshop

The methodology and survey organisation process, as along with the questionnaire verification process, were explained and discussed with all the partners during the survey preparation workshop (Hereinafter – Workshop). The main objective of the Workshop was to present the methodology and questionnaires to all the partners and to agree on it, as well as on the schedule and survey organisation procedures.

The online Workshop (via Ms Teams) took place on 15 February 2023 and 2-4 representatives from each project partner were invited to attend.

A week prior to the Workshop, survey documents (methodology and questionnaires), were distributed to all the partners to ensure that everyone conducting the survey was familiar with the survey methodology, questionnaires, and survey organisation procedures.

2.5 Questionnaires

To identify the factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas, two questionnaires have been developed. The first questionnaire is designed for end-users of bio-based solutions (adopters and non-adopters) and the second questionnaire is created for experts in one or more of the five bioeconomy themes. The structure and logic consistency of the questionnaire for end-users is provided in section 2.5.1, and the questionnaire for experts is outlined in section 2.5.2.

2.5.1 Questionnaire for end-users

This questionnaire focuses on individuals or small to medium sized organisations, whose primary profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes (Food & Agriculture, Forestry & Natural Habitats, Aquatic Systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials) and who mainly operate in rural areas, with their activities limited to the interests of the primary and secondary sectors.

This questionnaire aims to assess and evaluate the current performance of the European rural bioeconomy and to identify the factors that affect innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The questionnaire for end-users is designed to gather information about their awareness of the items that can be produced using bio-based products, their adoption of bio-based solutions (in case they are adopters), incentives that led them to become adopters, reasons why they are not adopters of bio-based solutions (in case of non-adopters), what drivers and barriers to adopting bio-based solutions they identify.

The survey employs a variety of question formats, including statements for respondents to agree or disagree with (e.g., using the Likert Scale), simple multiple-choice questions, and a few open-ended questions.

The questionnaire consists of 31 questions, which are divided into three main groups:

1. General information about the respondent.
2. Barriers and driving factors for adopting bio-based solutions.
3. Needs, ideas, and interests.

The first part of the questionnaire for end-users aims to collect **general information**, including:

- Sociodemographic characteristics: gender, age, education.
- Social characteristics: country, region.
- Business structure characteristics, such as bioeconomy sector in which they operate, legal form, and the size of their farm/enterprise, years of experience in the field of activity, level of awareness about innovative bio-based solutions, among other things. This group of questions are applicable to adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions. The detailed distribution of these questions applicability is provided in Table 3.

The *second part* of the questionnaire for end-users is designed for both adopters and non-adopters and aims at identifying barriers and driving factors for adopting bio-based solutions. These questions are designed to find out:

- The barriers that end-users must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions, the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions. The survey expects adopters to identify success factors, while non-adopters may highlight potential factors and barriers to adopt bio-based solutions. Additionally, respondents are asked for their opinions on the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products.

The third part of the questionnaire for end-users is designed for both adopters and non-adopters and aims at identifying the needs, ideas, and interests. These questions are designed to uncover:

- Existing needs, ideas, and interests regarding the adoption of bio-based solutions, specific needs when choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution, information about the bio-based products, factors that have the potential to speed up innovative bio-based solutions, and more.

GROUP OF QUESTIONS	QUESTIONS	APPLICABLE FOR...
General information	Q1. Gender Q2. Age Q3. Education Q4. Country Q5. Region (NUTS3) Q6. What is the legal form of your farm/enterprise? Q7. What is the size of your farm/enterprise? Q8. What is your experience in the field of activity? Q9. What is your level of awareness about innovative small scale the-bio-based solutions? Q10. I am aware that the following items can be produced using bio-based products Q11. In which of 5 bioeconomy sectors you are operating (multiple choice)? Q12. Are you adopting any bio-based solution?	Adopters and Non-adopters
	Q13. My innovative product/production process will continue to be relevant for society after 2030 Q14. What type of bio-based solutions you are adopting? Please specify. Q15. What is the scale at which the bio-based solution operates? Q16. Have you had any engagement with any of the following stakeholders to understand if and how your bio-based solution could become more sustainable (regenerative, inclusive, circular), applicable, replicable, etc. Q17. If your answer is YES to Q16, please explain what the nature and purpose of the engagement and/or consultation was with the relevant stakeholders. Please comment. Q18. What kind of incentives led you to become an adopter?	Adopters
	Q19. What are the reasons why you are not adopting innovative bio-based solutions? Q20. What kind of information would you need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution? Q21. Would you give it a try to begin adopting a bio-based solution if it were supported through subsidies? Q22. If your answer to Q21 is YES, which category of bio-based solution would you apply? Q23. Would you adopt bio-based solution if you could cooperate and share the costs with others	Non-adopters

Barriers and driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions	Q24. Identify the barriers your farm/organization has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions Q25. In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for biobased products? Q26. What are the main driving factors for adoption of bio-based solutions?	Adopters and non-adopters
Needs, ideas, and interests	Q27. What are your specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution? Q28. Does your farm or enterprise need support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions? Q29. If your answer to Q28 is YES, please specify what kind of support would you seek? Q30. In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas? Q31. If you are interested in being a part of BioRural ERBN please provide us with your contact details	Adopters and non-adopters

Table 3: The question groups and applicability of the end-users' questionnaire

The questionnaire for end-users will be provided on the e-survey platform. Depending on the needs, project partners will assist end-users in translating the questions into their national languages, explaining the questions, and/or helping to fill out the questionnaire. Regardless of the language in which the interview is conducted, the answers of the end-users' interviews must be filled out in the English language on the e-survey platform (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BIORURAL>).

2.5.2 Questionnaire for experts

This questionnaire focuses on the experts who have a high level of expertise in five Bioeconomy themes and can provide expertise into the needs, interests, innovation processes, capacities, barriers, driving factors, and the information needed to adopt bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The questionnaire for experts is designed to gather information about their expert opinion on the 5 bioeconomy themes, the bio-based innovation processes, capacities to adopt bio-based solutions, as well the driving factors and barriers that are affecting the development and successful adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas, as well as the information and support needs.

For expert interviews, a mixed type of questions will be used. The survey relies on asking experts to agree or disagree with statements representing different points of view (e.g., using the Likert Scale), and asking open-ended questions.

The questionnaire consists of 23 questions which are divided into three main groups:

1. General information about the respondent.
2. Barriers and driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions.
3. Needs, ideas, and interests.

The *first part* of the questionnaire for experts aims to collect **general** information on:

- Sociodemographic characteristics: gender, age, education.
- Social characteristics: country, region.

- Expertise in the field related to the 5 bioeconomy themes. It is considered that experts are those individuals who have high-level expertise (education and/or practice experience in one or some Bioeconomy themes). The detailed distribution of the questions is provided in Table 4.

The *second part* of the questionnaire for experts aims to collect their opinions on **barriers and driving factors** for adopting bio-based solutions:

- This group of questions is focuses on expert’s opinion about the current situation of the rural bioeconomy and the difference in rural regions, incentives, policies, and other driving, and restraining factors that influence the successful adoption of bio-based solutions. Moreover, experts are asked about the type of capacities, advisory, brokerage or support services that could help to increase the circular bioeconomy situation in rural areas.

The *third part* of the questionnaire for experts aims to collect experts’ opinion on **needs, ideas, and interests**:

- This group of questions is focused on hearing the experts’ opinions on types of stakeholders that could influence small scale produces covert to bio-based production/processing, the specific needs when choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution, what information is missing and what should be done to increase the rural circular bioeconomy and better adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas in both the short and long term.

GROUP OF QUESTIONS	QUESTIONS
General information	Q1. Country Q2. Gender Q3. Age Q4. Education Q5. What is your experience in the field of activity? Q6. What is you your expertise in the field of circular bioeconomy and the adoption of bio-bases solution. Q7. In which of 5 bioeconomy sectors you are operating as an expert
Barriers and driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions	Q8. What is your opinion about the current situation of the rural bioeconomy? Why the circular bioeconomy situation is so different in the rural regions? Q9. What kind of incentives are needed so that both the circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas are easier and more often developed and applied? Q10. What is your expert opinion, about the sufficiency and efficiency of current policy in rural regions to support the development and adoption of bio-based solutions? Q11. What are the main driving factors of rural small scale produces, SMEs to start developing and adopting bio-based solutions? Q12. What are the main barriers for adopters to develop bio-based solutions? Q13. What are the barriers for non-adopters to start developing the bio-bases materials? Q14. In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for biobased products? Q15. Does the membership with small producer’s groups/ cooperatives, etc., are helping better to overcome the challenges that adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions are facing? Q16. What capacities are needed to develop and adopt bio-based solutions in rural regions?

	Q17. Do you think the advisory/ brokerage services are well developed to support adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions? To your opinion, what kind of advice they need the most?
Needs, ideas, and interests	<p>Q18. Which type of stakeholders could influence small scale producers to convert to bio-based production/processing?</p> <p>Q19. What are the specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solutions?</p> <p>Q20. Do you think that the knowledge transfer system, the share of experience and replicability of innovative bio-based solutions are efficient and integrated (e.g., involving different types of stakeholders depending on their functional performance), etc.?</p> <p>Q21. What information is necessary to know about the bio-based products (for adopters and non-adopters)?</p> <p>Q22. What should be done to increase the rural circular bioeconomy and better adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas in a short and in a long time?</p> <p>Q23. If you are interested in being a part of BioRural ERBN Please provide us with your contact details).</p>

Table 4: The question groups of the experts' questionnaire

The questionnaire for experts will be provided on the e-survey platform, and depending on the needs, project partners will assist experts in translating the questions into their national languages, explain the questions, and/or help to fill out the questionnaire. Despite the fact in which language the interview was conducted, the answers of the experts' interviews must be filled out in the English language in the e-survey platform (https://ec.europa.eu/eu-survey/runner/BIORURAL_EXPERT).

To simplify the communication and the survey process between the end-users as well as experts and interviewers, some examples of bio-based solutions will be provided as a guide to better understand the concept and definitions. This will be particularly applicable and useful for non-adopters. Examples of biobased solutions are provided in Annex IV.

3 Survey results and discussion

3.1 Sampling stratification of the survey

3.1.1 Characteristics of the end-users

The “EUSurvey” platform was used to collect all the data from the end-users who participated in the survey. The data was downloaded from the platform as a spreadsheet and used for analysis. According to the project, the total sample of the survey was at least 400 end-users. In total, interviews with >400 end-users have been conducted in four regional RBPs. Each RBP consists of three or four countries (see Figure 2 for the assignment of countries to a specific RBP). In each study country, the project partners conducted interviews either by telephone or in person.

The survey was conducted from early March to mid-June 2023. During the survey process, interviewers asked questions and end-users responded. The total number of questionnaires was 422. After eliminating questionnaires that omitted important information or provided contradictory information, 417 valid questionnaires were obtained, giving an effective rate of 98.8%. The data sets (total N=417; North-West region’s N=82, North-East region’s N=123, South-West region’s N=102, South-East region’s N=110) were analysed using the chi-square test to test for differences between the groups of end-users according to regional RBPs, bioeconomy themes, localisation (remoteness) of the end-users regions, and socio-demographic and business structural characteristics.

Project partners in four regional RBPs conducted end-user surveys based on the agreed sampling stratification (see Methodology of end-users’ survey section). As a result, all five bioeconomy themes were covered, the targeted number of end-users was exceeded in four bioeconomy themes and there was a negligible shortfall in the case of food and agriculture (Table 5).

Bioeconomy theme		Region				Total
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East	
Food and Agriculture	N	47	54	63	70	234
	%	47.5%	44.3%	51.0%	54.5%	49.5%
Forestry and natural habitats	N	9	22	35	18	84
	%	13.1%	19.7%	26.9%	16.4%	20.3%
Water Systems	N	8	6	8	6	28
	%	11.5%	9.8%	5.8%	7.3%	8.2%
Bioenergy	N	6	13	12	7	38
	%	8.2%	14.8%	11.5%	7.3%	10.7%
Biomaterials	N	12	7	5	9	33
	%	19.7%	11.5%	4.8%	14.5%	11.4%
Total	N	82	102	123	110	417
	%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 5: Number and percentage of the end-users interviewed by bioeconomy themes in each RBP and in total sample (based on Table 1)

The number and percentage of the end-users surveyed by legal form varied slightly according to the legal form of all end-users surveyed: less than half (176) were natural persons and more than half (241) were legal entities. Only in the North-West RBP did the number of natural persons surveyed exceed the number of legal entities surveyed (Table 6).

Legal form		Region				Total
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East	
Natural person ¹	N	46	37	35	58	176
	%	56.1%	36.3%	28.5%	52.7%	42.2%
Legal entity ²	N	36	65	88	52	241
	%	43.9%	63.7%	71.5%	47.3%	57.8%
Total	N	82	102	123	110	417
	%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 6: Number and percentage of the end-users interviewed by legal form of the farm and enterprise in each RBP and in total sample

Note: ¹ Natural person involves Natural person* and Sole proprietorship**; ² Legal entity involves Legal person*, Group holding*, Common land unit*, Partnership, co-operatives, associations**, Limited liability enterprise**; * reflects legal form for a farm; ** reflects legal form for an enterprise.

The percentage of the end-users surveyed in each size class of the farm/enterprise by number of persons employed (less than 10 persons employed, from 10 to 249 persons employed) varied considerably. In all regions, between 65% and almost 80% of the end-users came from micro farms/enterprises (Table 7).

Size class of the farm/enterprise by persons employed		Region				Total
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East	
Less than 10 persons employed	N	61	72	79	87	299
	%	74.4%	70.6%	64.2%	79.1%	71.7%
From 10 to 249 persons employed	N	21	30	44	23	118
	%	25.6%	29.4%	35.8%	20.9%	28.3%
Total	N	82	102	123	110	417
	%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 7: Number and percentage of the end-users interviewed by size classes in each RBP and in total sample

The majority of the end-users surveyed (more than a third in each regional RBP) had more than 20 years of experience in the field of activity. The smallest group (only about one out of 10) of the end-users had 16-20 years of experience in the field of activity (Table 8).

Experience in the field of activity		Region				Total
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East	
Less than 5 years	N	21	14	13	19	67
	%	25.6%	13.7%	10.6%	17.3%	16.1%
5-10 years	N	16	19	25	21	81
	%	19.5%	18.6%	20.3%	19.1%	19.4%
11-15 years	N	7	16	28	18	69
	%	8.5%	15.7%	22.8%	16.4%	16.5%
16-20 years	N	9	11	15	10	45
	%	11.0%	10.8%	12.2%	9.1%	10.8%
More than 20 years	N	29	42	42	42	155
	%	35.4%	41.2%	34.1%	38.2%	37.2%
Total	N	82	102	123	110	417
	%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 8: Number and percentage of the end-users interviewed by years of experience in each RBP and in total sample

In the South-East RBP, less than half of the end-users surveyed were adopters of any bio-based solution in food and agriculture, whereas in the other four bioeconomy themes more than half of the end-users surveyed were adopters of bio-based solutions. The peculiarity of this region – a tenth of the end-users surveyed in the biomaterials were non-adopters, whereas all the end-users surveyed with activities in biomaterials were adopters in the other three regions. In the South-West RBP, as many as half of the end-users surveyed were adopters. The unique feature of this region is that all end-users were adopters of biomaterials and water systems. In the North-East RBP, more than three-quarters of the end-users surveyed were adopters. A particular feature of this region is that there were no non-adopters taking part in the survey on the themes of biomaterials and bioenergy. In the North-West RBP, bioenergy, water systems, forestry and natural habitats, and food and agriculture had the second lowest percentage of the non-adopters of a bio-based solution. In the total sample, the lowest percentage of the non-adopters was found in biomaterials, while the highest percentage of the non-adopters was found in food and agriculture (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Percentage of the end-users interviewed by adoption of bio-based solution in each RBP and in total sample

According to the localisation (remoteness) of the end-user regions (North Macedonia is not included in the classification of remoteness), about one-fifth of the regions were close to a city, and four-fifths were remote. The proportion of the end-users surveyed from remote regions is very different in the North-West region (almost 94%) (Table 9).

End-users' localization in categories of NUTS-3 regions		Region				Total
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East*	
Regions, close to a city	N	5	21	28	23	77
	%	6.1%	20.6%	22.8%	28.0%	19.8%
Remote regions	N	77	81	95	59	312
	%	93.9%	79.4%	77.2%	72.0%	80.2%

Table 9: Number and percentage of the end-users interviewed by remoteness of rural areas in each RBP and in total sample (based on Table 1)

* Without North Macedonia whose NUTS regions are not classified by remoteness.

Note: For the survey, end-users were selected from rural areas located in four categories of NUTS-3 regions such as “predominantly rural regions, close to a city” and “predominantly rural, remote regions”, as well as “intermediate regions, close to a city” and “intermediate remote regions”.

3.1.2 Characteristics of the experts

Project partners in four regional RBPs conducted expert surveys based on the agreed methodology provided in the previous chapter. The experts represented all the RBP regions and provided explicit opinions due to their experience in the field.

As a result, most experts were representers of food and agriculture and forestry and natural habitats bioeconomy themes. All regions of surveying were well covered. The number of experts by age varied slightly in three age groups (see Table 10) according to the analysed data, but one group of age was most exhibited: slightly less than half (19) were in the 40-49 age group.

Age		Region				Total		
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East			
25-39	N	1	2	1	5	9	19.6%	
40-49	N	4	3	5	7	19	41.3%	
50-59	N	2	2	3	-	7	15.2%	
60-74	N	4	3	1	3	11	23.9%	
Total		N	11	10	10	15	46	100%

Table 10: Number and percentage of the experts interviewed by age in each RBP and in total.

The percentage of the experts surveyed according to their education was highest with a Ph.D. degree, around two-thirds of the 46 experts (Table 11). A similar structure of experts by education in all regional RBPs.

Education		Region				Total		
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East			
Bachelor	N	-	1	-	1	2	4.3%	
Master	N	4	3	3	3	13	28.3%	
Doctorate	N	7	6	7	11	31	67.4%	
Total		N	11	10	10	15	46	100%

Table 11: Number and percentage of the experts interviewed by age range in each RBP and in total sample

Around two-thirds of the experts represented the research field as their main activity. This tendency was recognisable in all RBPs. Policymakers and advisers were representing 11 experts (accordingly 8.7% and 13.04%) (Table 12). The smallest number was the experts as developers – 13.04% of all the experts.

Occupation and field of expertise		Region				Total		
		North-West	South-West	North-East	South-East			
Practical activity	N	1	2	2	1	6	13.0%	
Research	N	6	5	7	11	29	63.0%	
Policy maker	N	2	-	1	1	4	8.7%	
Adviser	N	2	3	-	2	7	15.2%	
Total		N	11	10	10	15	46	100%

Table 12: Number and percentage of the experts interviewed by field of their occupation in each RBP and in total sample

3.2 Survey results analysis and interpretation

3.2.1 Bio-based solutions in rural areas

About two-thirds of the adopters surveyed adopt bio-based products and/or bio-based processes, almost half of them adopts bio-based technologies, and only very few percent of the adopters surveyed adopt other bio-based solutions. Almost two-thirds of the non-adopters surveyed said that they would apply bio-based product, more than half of the non-adopters chose bio-based technology, and less than half said that they would apply bio-based process (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Bio-based solutions by the end-users

Note: **Bio-based product** refers to products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees, or animals (the biomass can have undergone physical, chemical, or biological treatment); **Bio-based technology** focuses on bio-based technological applications during degradation of by-products, waste, residues and production of valuable products or energy from renewable resource; and **Bio-based process** means switching to using biological resources and biological processing methods in a sustainable way).

Across regional RBPs, there is a statistically significant difference between how the adopters surveyed answered this question (Fig. 6). The highest percentage of bio-based products is adopted in the North-West RBP (8 out of 10), while the lowest percentage - in the South-West RBP (about half). The highest percentage of bio-based technologies is adopted in the South-East RBP, while the lowest percentage - in the North-East RBP. The highest percentage of other bio-based solutions is adopted in the South-East RBP, while the lowest percentage - in the North-East RBP.

*** Significant at p<0.01; ** significant at p<0.05.

Figure 6: Bio-based solutions adopted by the end-users according to RBP (N=281)

At the bioeconomy theme level, there are statistically significant differences between how the adopters surveyed specified the choice of bio-based product and bio-based technology (Fig. 7). Almost 90% of the adopters surveyed in biomaterials, while only slightly more than half of the adopters surveyed in forestry and natural habitats adopt bio-based products. In terms of bio-based technology, about three-quarters of the adopters surveyed in bioenergy, while only about a third of the adopters surveyed in water systems adopt it.

Figure 7: Bio-based solutions adopted by the end-users according to bioeconomy themes (N=281)

Statistically significant differences between how the adopters surveyed indicated the choice of bio-based product and bio-based technology are identified by education level, legal form of farm/enterprise, remoteness of regions, or size of farm/enterprise (Fig. 8). Two-thirds of the adopters who have advanced or intermediate education adopt bio-based product, whereas only about one-fifth of the adopters who have a basic education level adopt bio-based product. Statistically significant differences in the opinions of the adopters surveyed are also identified according to the legal form of farm/enterprise: slightly more than half of legal entities surveyed and about one third of natural persons surveyed adopt bio-based technology. By remoteness of regions, about two-thirds of the adopters surveyed from rural areas close to a city, and more than half of the adopters surveyed from remote rural areas adopt bio-based product. There are statistically significant differences in the opinions of the adopters according to the size of the farm/enterprise: more than half of small and medium-sized farms/enterprises and less than half of micro farms/enterprises adopt bio-based technology.

Figure 8: Bio-based solutions adopted by the end-users according to their socio-demographic and business structural characteristics (N=281)

Adopters were also asked what is the scale at which the bio-based solution operates. About two-thirds of the adopters surveyed said that the bio-based solution operates at a farm/enterprise scale. About a third chose specific industry in rural areas and community level, whereas only one in seven chose village scale (Fig. 9). There is a statistically significant difference between how the adopters answered the question across RBPs. The scale at which the bio-based solution operates is very split. For instance, 44-91% of the adopters said that the bio-based solutions operate at farm/enterprise scale, 8-23% at village scale, 16-48% at community scale, 18-38% at specific industry in

rural areas scale. The ultimate singularity is the North-East RBP, where even 91% of the adopters surveyed said that bio-based solutions operate at farm/enterprise scale.

There is a statistically significant difference in the results of the adopters' answers to this question according to the legal form of the farm/enterprise. Almost two-thirds of legal entities and six-sevenths of natural persons said that the bio-based solution operates at farm/enterprise scale, whereas about one third of legal entities and one sixth of natural persons stated that the bio-based solution operates at specific industry in rural areas scale.

A statistically significant difference in the results of the adopters' answers to this question is also found according to the localisation (remoteness) of the end-user regions. 16% of the adopters surveyed from rural areas close to a city and 4% of the adopters surveyed from remote rural areas said that the bio-based solution operates at village scale.

What is the scale at which the bio-based solution operates?

*** Significant at p<0.01; ** significant at p<0.05; * significant at p<0.1.

Figure 9: The scale at which the end-users bio-based solution operates (N=281)

Adopters were asked about their engagement with the listed stakeholders to understand if and how their bio-based solution could become more sustainable, applicable, replicable, etc. 240 out of 281 adopters indicated that they had engagement with the stakeholders (Fig. 10). The largest proportion (more than half) of the adopters that engage with stakeholders do so with customers, suppliers, researchers, and external advisors.

Across RBPs, there is a statistically significant difference between how the adopters surveyed responded to this question (Fig. 11). Compared to the other RBPs, the North-East RBP had the highest level of engagement with stakeholders, such as customers, suppliers, researchers, external advisors, associations, and own employees (between half and three-quarters of the adopters). The South-East RBP's adopters surveyed (who engage with stakeholders) were most engaged with researchers (more than half), from the North-East RBP - own employees (three-

quarters), from the South-West RBP – external advisors (more than half), from the North-West RBP - researchers (more than half).

Figure 10: End-users' engagement with the stakeholders (N=240)

Have you had any engagement with any of the following stakeholders to understand if and how your bio-based solution could become more sustainable (regenerative, inclusive, circular), applicable, replicable, etc.?

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 11: End-users' engagement with the stakeholders across regions (N=240)

A statistically significant difference in the results of the adopters' answers to this question is also found according to the localisation (remoteness) of the end-user regions. Compared to remote rural areas, the adopters surveyed from rural areas close to a city had more engagement with customers, researchers, authority of legislator, and own employees (37-65% of the adopters from rural areas close to a city vs 17-43% of the adopters surveyed from remote rural areas). However, adopters from remote rural areas had more engagement with other stakeholders (not listed in the question) than adopters from rural areas close to a city (fifth and tenth, respectively).

There are statistically significant differences in how the end-users surveyed with different socio-demographic and business structure characteristics answered the question about the engagement with stakeholders (Fig. 12). Legal entities are more engaged with customers, suppliers, researchers, thematic networks, and own employees than natural persons. The exception is other stakeholder - natural persons (almost a fifth) are more engaged with them than legal entities (a tenth).

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 12: End-users' engagement with the stakeholders by socio-demographic and businesses structural characteristics (N=240)

Farms/enterprises over ten years of experience are the most engaged with associations and own employees. An interesting finding is that the adopters surveyed with a basic education level had not engaged with customers and researchers at all. In the same vein, the end-users surveyed with advanced education level are the most engaged with customers and researchers.

At the size of the farm/enterprise level, almost two-thirds of the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises surveyed that engage with stakeholders (half of the micro farms/enterprises) engage with suppliers, slightly more than half engage with their own employees (less than half of the micro farms/enterprises), while a higher percentage of the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises engage with associations (slightly less than half) than the micro farms/enterprises (one third).

The experts also have been asked for their opinion on which type of stakeholders could influence small-scale producers to convert to bio-based production/processing. According to the experts, several types of stakeholders can play a significant role in influencing small-scale producers to convert to bio-based production and processing in rural regions. Cooperatives/producer organisations could initiate the implementation of innovations through cooperation. Scientists/scientific institutions would help to create new or adapt already innovative production and processing technologies, new products, or update part of the production processes. Branch business associations could represent the interests of small producers, seeking financial and non-financial support from the authorities. Some experts say that the biggest impact could be on local governments at the level of decision-makers, to develop business in rural areas as well. Consumers and biomass providers are very important. Demand and realisation are the key spheres influencing the process of conversion. Additionally, EU, national, regional, local government institutions can be active stakeholders as well as cooperatives, agricultural/technical advisors, other producers/processors, universities/research organisations could be active in the field.

These stakeholders can provide support, resources, expertise, and incentives that encourage producers to adopt more sustainable and environmentally friendly practices. Here are some key types of stakeholders: Government Agencies and Policy Makers, Industry Associations and Clusters, Specialised Research and Academic Institutions, Financial Institutions and Investors, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), Local Communities and Consumers as well as Suppliers and Distributors, Chambers of Commerce and Business Networks, Local and Regional Authorities, Innovation Hubs, and Incubators, etc.

Moreover, society should focus on promoting and facilitating increased engagement between adopters and stakeholders, particularly in regions with lower engagement, to enhance the sustainability, applicability, and replicability of bio-based solutions. It is essential to foster collaboration and partnership among government agencies, industry associations, research institutions, financial entities, NGOs, local communities, and other stakeholders to provide comprehensive support, resources, and incentives for small-scale producers in rural regions to transition towards bio-based production, thereby promoting sustainability and innovation in these areas.

We asked the adopters to answer the question about the relevance of their innovative product/production process for society after 2030 (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: End-users opinion on the relevance of their innovative product/production process for society after 2030 (N=281)

In total, 94% of the adopters surveyed think that their innovative product/production process will be relevant for society after 2030. There is a statistically significant difference between the opinions of the adopters surveyed

according to the legal form of the farm/enterprise: about 95% of legal entities answered “yes” and about 5% were unsure, whereas 93% of natural persons answered “yes”, 3% answered “no” and 4% were unsure about the relevance of their innovative product/production process for society after 2030.

There is also a statistically significant difference between the opinions of the adopters surveyed across different RBPs. In the South-West RBP, the lowest percentage (six-sevenths) of the adopters surveyed think that their innovative product/production process will be relevant for society after 2030, and around one-seventh of the adopters surveyed in this RBP are not sure about the relevance of their product/production process for society after 2030. In the South-East, North-East, and North-West RBPs, more than 90% of the adopters surveyed think that their innovative product/production process will be relevant for society after 2030.

3.2.2 Incentives, barriers and driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions

3.2.2.1 Incentives to become adopters of bio-based solutions

When asked adopters about the kinds of incentives to become adopters, the largest proportion (two-thirds) of the adopters surveyed chose economic benefit (Fig. 14). The second most frequently (slightly more than half of responses) chosen answer was enhanced product performance and/or functionalities.

Figure 14: Incentives to lead the end-users to become adopters of bio-based solutions in rural areas (N=281)

The responses of the adopters surveyed to the question about the incentives that led them to become adopters differed statistically significantly between the RBPs (Fig. 15). According to the answers to this question, the North-East RBP is very different from the other RBPs. In this RBP, around seven-eighths of the adopters surveyed (41-65% of the responses in the other RBPs) said that easily replicable good practice is the incentive that led them to become adopters, 4 out of 10 adopters surveyed (16-26% of the responses in the other RBPs) said that a positive framework to switch to bio-based solution is the incentive that led them to become adopters, slightly more than half (24-37% in the other RBPs) selected government subsidies and/or other support schemes, around five-sevenths (43-55% in the other RBPs) chose enhanced product performance and/or functionalities, slightly less than half (11-20% in the other RBPs) selected competition with successful brand owners' companies, and almost 90% (41-65% in the other RBPs) selected economic benefit.

What kind of incentives led you to become an adopter?

*** Significant at p<0.01.

Figure 15: Incentives to lead the end-users to become adopters of bio-based solutions in by regional RBP (N=281)

The incentives that led end-users to become adopters of bio-based solutions also differed statistically significantly according to the business structural characteristics and remoteness of rural areas (Fig. 16). The answers to this question are very split by education - about 6 out of 10 adopters surveyed with 11-15 and more than 20 years of experience said that easy replicable practice is an incentive to become an adopter, between 41-73% of the adopters surveyed with different years of experience said that enhanced product performance and/or functionalities is an incentive. In terms of demand, public perceptions, and consumer behaviour on “bio-based” alternatives megatrends, between 53% and 67% of the adopters surveyed said that this is an incentive. However, the exception is the adopters surveyed with 5-10 years of experience - only around a third of them said that this is an incentive. In terms of economic benefit, around three quarters of the adopters surveyed with more than 11 years of experience said that this is an incentive to become an adopter, while only about half of the adopters surveyed with less than 11 years of experience said this is an incentive.

According to the size of the farm/enterprise, about one third of the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises and about one fourth of the micro farms/enterprises chose competition with successful brand owners' companies that are already investing in bio-based alternatives as an incentive to become an adopter. In comparison, around three quarters of the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises and around three-fifths of the micro farms/enterprises chose economic benefit as an incentive to become an adopter.

At the bioeconomy theme level, there is also a statistically significant difference in the responses of the adopters. The largest proportion of the adopters surveyed from forestry and natural habitats, and food and agriculture said that easy replicable good practice (slightly more than half) and positive legislative framework to switch to bio-based solution (a third) are incentives to become an adopter. When it comes to economic benefit, the answers are more split – about 4 out of 10 adopters surveyed from biomaterials/bio-based products and 8 out of 10 adopters surveyed from bioenergy chose economic benefit as an incentive to become an adopter.

Government subsidies and/or other support schemes are an incentive to become an adopter for a third of the adopters surveyed from rural areas close to a city and for half of the adopters surveyed from remote rural areas.

What kind of incentives led you to become an adopter?

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 16: Incentives to lead end-users to become an adopter of bio-based solutions by businesses structural characteristics, and remoteness of rural areas (N=281)

According to the expert's survey results, promoting the circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas requires a multi-faceted approach that goes beyond economic incentives. A range of non-economic incentives can play a crucial role in promoting the development and application of circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas. According to the experts, these incentives help create an enabling environment that encourages stakeholders to adopt sustainable practices and technologies.

The summary of expert's survey results has highlighted similarities between the different RBP, and the incentives needed to foster the development and application of circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas. Despite the regional differences, all those incentives can be grouped to:

- **Capacity building, education, and training.** According to the experts, education or technical expertise is needed for the possibilities offered by the rural bioeconomy. In particular, education and support are needed for small and medium-sized enterprises, which have the greatest potential to be the drivers of these processes, which,

with the processing of waste and by-products from agriculture and forestry, regardless of the production of bio-fuel or in other types of useful products, could profit significantly. Therefore, providing training programs for rural residents in bio-based industries can enhance local capabilities and employment opportunities, and increase the competitiveness of rural areas. Also, it has been highlighted that peer-to-peer learning and demonstration of good practices are great incentives that are easy to accept and adopt.

- **Collaborating and Networking.** Cross-knowledge transfer between business sectors, Governmental bodies, NGOs, research and education institutions, pilot projects and initiatives at all levels, including public awareness campaigns can inform rural communities about the benefits of bio-based solutions and the circular bioeconomy. According to the experts, there will have to be incentives for the capitalisation of small producers and SMEs. Moreover, it is necessary to have incentives for collaboration and union between the different producers in order to have an efficient approach to the use of these bioeconomy practices. It has been highlighted, (especially in SW RBP), that greater and more intimate interaction with the populations of rural regions, may strengthen that comprehension. Therefore, the incentives may be communication activities or even visits to locations/pilots with similar problems but that have already introduced and successfully adopted innovative bio-based solutions.
- **Financial incentives.** Experts' survey results have demonstrated the important of grants and subsidies to support research, development, and implementation of circular bioeconomy projects and small-scale bio-based business in rural areas. Also, there are needed coherent strategies to overcome the lack of financial resources, developing and/or marking the adequate technology available locally, supporting the rural-urban cooperation etc.
- **Regulatory and Policy Incentives.** There is a viral opinion, that governments can implement regulations that reward businesses for adopting circular and bio-based practices, also by simplifying the permitting process for bio-based projects can reduce administrative hurdles.

The experts agreed, that by combining these incentives, governments, organisations, and communities can create a supportive ecosystem that encourages the development and application of circular bioeconomy solutions in rural areas. This approach should be tailored to the specific needs and challenges of each region to maximise its effectiveness.

Promoting the development and application of circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in European rural areas is essential for sustainable and circular economic growth, environmental conservation, and rural community resilience. Here are recommendations on key factors that can play a crucial role in achieving these goals. First of all conduct awareness campaigns and educational programs tailored to rural communities to build the skills and knowledge needed for bio-based businesses and circular practices in rural areas, also to inform residents, farmers, and entrepreneurs about the benefits and opportunities of circular bioeconomy and bio-based solutions.

Moreover, it has been observed the need to develop collaborative platforms, research, and innovation hubs that help to facilitate and transfer technology and knowledge from urban innovation centres to rural areas through outreach programs, technology parks, and partnerships with research institutions that focus on bio-based technologies, sustainable agriculture, and circular economy practices.

Furthermore, it is essential to establish clear and supportive regulatory frameworks that encourage innovation and circular practices, organic agriculture, and agroecological approaches that contribute to circularity and socio-economic sustainability and reduce environmental impact. Those efforts should be focused on tailoring incentive programs to regional contexts, with a particular emphasis on the promotion of easily replicable good practices, positive frameworks for transitioning to bio-based solutions, government subsidies and support schemes, enhanced product performance, and economic benefits, as these were the most influential factors cited by adopters, thereby encouraging wider adoption and sustainability in rural regions.

3.2.2.2 Barriers to the adoption of bio-based solutions

We asked end-users to identify the barriers their farm/enterprise has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions (Fig. 17). Most end-users surveyed (more than half) agreed with the statement that lack of financial capital is a barrier to adopting bio-based solutions. The end-users surveyed showed the greatest disagreement (less than half) with the statement that uncertainty about environmental benefits is the barrier their farm/enterprise has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions.

Identify the barriers your farm/organization have/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions.

Figure 17: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas (N=417)

A statistically significant difference is found in how the end-users from different RBPs responded to the question about the barriers (Fig. 18). In the South-East RBP, the highest percentage of the end-users surveyed (about 6 out of 10) agreed that lack of knowledge is the main barrier for end-users to adopt bio-based solutions, while the highest percentage of the end-users surveyed in this region disagreed (about 4 out of 10) that uncertainty around environmental benefits is a barrier to adopt bio-based solutions.

In comparison, the highest percentage (more than half) of the end-users surveyed agreed that lack of clear guidelines or there is not a national bioeconomy strategy in action is the main barrier to adopting bio-based solutions, and less than half of the end-users surveyed disagreed that uncertainty around environmental benefits is a barrier for bio-based solutions in the North-East RBP. In the South-West RBP, two-thirds of the end-users surveyed most strongly agreed that lack of knowledge is a barrier to adopting bio-based solutions, while half of responses represented disagreement that uncertainty around environmental benefits is a barrier to adopting bio-based solutions. Slightly more than half of the end-users surveyed in the North-West RBP agreed that legislative barriers are important barriers to adopting bio-based solutions and less than half of the end-users surveyed in this region disagreed that uncertainty around environmental benefits is the barrier to the adoption of bio-based solutions.

Identify the barriers your farm/organization has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions.

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 18: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions by regional RBP (N=417)

At the bioeconomy theme level, a statistically significant difference is found in the way the end-users perceived lack of knowledge as a barrier they have to overcome to adopt bio-based solutions (Fig. 19). Across all bioeconomy themes, the end-users surveyed agreed (42-58%) that lack of knowledge is a barrier their farm/enterprise has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions. The only exception was for water systems where slightly less than one third of the end-users surveyed agreed and slightly more than one third of the end-users surveyed disagreed that lack of knowledge is a barrier to adopting bio-based solutions.

Identify the barriers your farm/organization has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions
 Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

** Significant at p<0.05.

Figure 19: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions by bioeconomy themes (N=417)

A statistically significant difference between how adopters and non-adopters responded to the question about the barriers to adopting bio-based solutions is identified (Fig. 20). Technical capacity and legislative barriers (almost half of respondents there) were rated by the non-adopters surveyed as highly important barriers to overcome to adopt bio-based solutions. About 50% and 36% (the same percentage for two barriers) of the non-adopters surveyed disagreed that uncertainty around environmental benefits and incompatibility with existing processes or high replacement costs as well as feedstock or ingredient supply uncertainties, respectively, are the main barriers to adopting bio-based solutions. In comparison, lack of knowledge and technical capacity (perceived as such by about 70% and 60% of respondents there, respectively) were identified as the main barriers to adopting bio-based solutions by the adopters surveyed. Almost a third and a fifth of the adopters surveyed disagreed that uncertainty around environmental benefits and legislative barriers, respectively, are the main barriers to adopting bio-based solutions.

Identify the barriers your farm/organization has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions.
 Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at p<0.01; ** significant at p<0.05; * significant at p<0.1.

Figure 20: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions (N=417)

For several of the barriers listed, there is a statistically significant difference between the perceptions of legal entities and natural persons (Fig. 21). The largest differences between the perceptions of barriers by legal entities and natural persons were based on lack of knowledge, partnerships, clear guidelines or the absence of a national

bioeconomy strategy, uncertainty about environmental benefits, uncertainties about the supply of feedstock or ingredient, incompatibility with existing processes or high replacement costs, higher life-cycle costs to buyers, and legislative barriers. Slightly more than half of legal entities agreed that the lack of clear guidelines or the absence of a national bioeconomy strategy in action is an important barrier to adopting bio-based solutions. In comparison, slightly more than half of natural persons agreed that lack of knowledge is an important barrier to adopting bio-based solutions.

Figure 21: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions by legal form of farms and enterprises (N=417)

Similarly, there are statistically significant differences in the perception of two of the barriers listed between the end-users surveyed in rural areas close to a city and remote rural areas (Fig. 22). About 4 out of 10 end-users surveyed in both remote rural areas and rural areas close to a city considered insufficient consumer interests/awareness as an important barrier to adopting bio-based solutions. In the same vein, 45% of the end-users surveyed in rural areas close to a city (34% of respondents in remote rural areas) did not consider uncertainty around environmental benefits to be an important barrier to adopting bio-based solutions.

Figure 22: Barriers for the end-users to the adoption of bio-based solutions by remoteness of rural areas (N=417)

The development and adoption of bio-based solutions, while beneficial, can also face several barriers that hinder their widespread implementation. These barriers vary depending on the specific context for the region, but here are some common challenges that, according to experts, adopters and non-adopters are facing (Table 13):

Barriers for adopters	Barriers for non-adopters
<p>Lack of qualified personnel. According to the experts, the lack of qualified personnel can impede progress, and the lack of technical expertise on value chain optimisation is a barrier to adopting bio-based solutions.</p>	<p>Lack of professional capacity. The lack of professional capacity can have a significant impact on the adoption of bio-based solutions in various ways. First, Bio-based solutions often require specialised technical knowledge insufficient professional capacity means there may not be individuals with the necessary expertise to develop, implement, and maintain these solutions effectively.</p>
<p>Complex policy regulations and inconsistent policies. According to experts' survey results, the complex policy regulations, ambiguous standards, and inconsistent policies are creating uncertainty for businesses, affecting decision-making and hindering the development of bio-based solutions, as well as the limited access to financing (including loans, grants, and venture capital) is crucial for scaling up bio-based projects.</p>	<p>Insufficient of policy regulations. Experts have mentioned that there is still an absence of policy measures and funds to support and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas.</p>
<p>Limited or restricted funding opportunities. A lack of available funding options or stringent lending criteria can hinder development efforts. According to experts, developing innovative bio-based solutions often involves risk and uncertainty, especially if the technologies are not well-established. This can deter investors and businesses from pursuing these solutions. Financing, bureaucracy in adopting the transition, regulation (e.g., classification/declassification of waste), the interconnection between the rural adopter and R&D entities, product cost and price, market, etc.</p>	<p>Limited funding and investments. Adopters, non-adopters may face challenges in accessing funding and investment for transitioning to bio-based solutions.</p>
<p>Knowledge gaps and accessibility to information. According to the experts, there is a lack of information and poor availability of information about innovative and sustainable bio-based solutions. A large part of the information is available in English, which is also an obstacle for part of the population. But there are more macro barriers for successful bio-based solutions implementation, and they are related to lack of finance, not ensuring the profitability of implemented solutions, lack of incentives for the development of bioactivities, lack of infrastructure, lack of technical skills and knowledge, limited possibilities of new products to market access, regulatory barriers, and dependence on traditional practices. Addressing these barriers will require a coordinated effort from all stakeholders to create a supportive environment for the development of bio-based solutions.</p>	<p>Knowledge gaps. Limited understanding of bio-based solutions, their benefits, and potential applications. A lack of awareness can lead to reluctance to explore these alternatives. Moreover, the non-adopters may perceive bio-based solutions as expensive to develop and implement, without a clear understanding of potential long-term cost savings or benefits. Also, novel technologies and processes, such as bio-based solutions, come with inherent risks and uncertainties. Non-adopters might be risk-averse and hesitant to invest in unproven technologies. Non-adopters have a lack of knowledge, stereotypes, adherence to conventional product production, too little understanding of changes in the bioeconomy and product markets, lack of incentives and pressure for governmental institutions.</p>
<p>Poor infrastructure. Limited infrastructure in rural areas can significantly affect the adoption of bio-based solutions in several ways. First, insufficient transportation infrastructure can make it challenging for rural communities to access the necessary feedstock materials for bio-based solutions. Second, the absence of processing and production facilities for bio-based solutions can be a major barrier. Rural areas may lack the necessary infrastructure for converting biomass into biofuels, biochemicals, or other products. Without access to these facilities, potential adopters have no means to convert raw materials into usable bio-based products, etc.</p>	
<p>Poor collaboration culture. A poor collaboration culture can have a significant negative impact on the adoption of bio-based solutions. In a culture where collaboration is lacking, individuals and organisations are less likely to share their knowledge, expertise, and best practices related to bio-based solutions. This can result in a lack of awareness and understanding of these technologies and their benefits. Collaborative efforts often uncover synergies that can lead to more efficient and effective solutions. In the absence of collaboration, these</p>	<p>Lack of cooperation. Lack of cooperation with other farmers and producers, lack of contact with other stakeholders in the regions, affects the introduction of new solutions at the regional scale.</p>

synergies may go unnoticed, leading to missed opportunities for optimising the adoption of bio-based technologies.	
Low technological level. Lack of access to mature technologies and the technical and engineering know-how needed to optimise the combination of technologies.	Lack of know-how. There is lack of know-how and technologies and lack of human resources with appropriate skills. According to experts, non-adopters need more information about developing bio-based solutions, more coordinated effort between policy-makers, investors, and other stakeholders, and provided financial and technical support, creating market demand, and developing policy frameworks that support the circular bioeconomy.
Insufficient Investments in Research, technology, and infrastructure. Transitioning to bio-based solutions often requires significant investment in research, technology, equipment, and infrastructure, thus the High Initial Costs particularly challenging small-scale producers and SMEs with limited capital resources. Moreover, developing and implementing bio-based solutions may demand specialised knowledge in biotechnology, process optimisation, and other technical areas.	Lack of demonstrations. The good practice/ lighthouse examples from outside one sector could provide ideas and possible solutions to tackle the same challenges.

Table 13: The barriers for adopters and non-adopters to adopt and develop the bio-based solutions

To address the lack of professional capacity and promote the adoption of bio-based solutions, several strategies can be considered like training and education which are useful to equip individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge related to bio-based technologies and practices, as technical assistance and mentoring to individuals and organisations involved in bio-based projects to ensure they have access to expert guidance. Moreover, investment in capacity-building initiatives, including professional development, certifications, and degree programs related to bio-based technology and sustainability. The professional capacity can be increased when fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing networks among professionals in the bio-based industry, facilitating the exchange of best practices/lighthouses and lessons learned.

To understand the barriers in-depth, the experts have been asked what their opinion is, does the membership with small producer’s groups/ cooperatives, etc., helps better to overcome the challenges that adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions are facing.

According to the expert’s survey results, membership with small producer groups, cooperatives, and similar organisations can indeed help both adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions overcome many of the challenges they face. These groups offer various benefits that can facilitate the adoption and development of bio-based solutions. Also, it could be a helpful strategy for adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions to overcome the challenges they face. Following experts’ opinion, in North-West and North-East RBPs the cooperation could increase the overall scale of production, which eliminates many problems, such as lack of funds for new solutions; the scale of product supply to the market being too small; improved sales management, and marketing; expansion of existing markets and search for new markets; the load on new production equipment, etc.

Experts have given specific importance to the cooperative or producer groups because their help for the members with their products along the entire value chain is even better when the cooperative is involved in the whole value chain. According to the experts, it is mostly applicable for South-East RBP. This is considered as a win-win situation where producers can organise and get a better price for their product allowing them to make investments in bio-based solutions which in turn improve their production and allow them to get a higher price and has positive externalities for the environment.

Moreover, experts pointed out in the South-West RBP, the role of associations and cooperatives is fundamental for the adoption of these practices, due to what I mentioned earlier: increasing the knowledge available about these practices through the technical body of these structures, and the increase in scale that makes these practices more viable and profitable. We believe that these structures are fundamental and should be recommended and supported to promote good bioeconomy practices adapted to the reality of each one of its associates.

Based on the responses from end-users regarding the barriers to adopting bio-based solutions, it has been noticed that a significant percentage of end-users identified “lack of financial capital” as a barrier (less than two-thirds), financial support programs and initiatives should be developed to help alleviate this obstacle, making it more financially feasible for farms and enterprises to transition to bio-based solutions. Furthermore, recognising that end-users generally disagree with “uncertainty about environmental benefits” as a significant barrier (less than half), efforts should be made to provide clear and accessible information regarding the environmental advantages of bio-based solutions, ensuring that potential adopters are well-informed about the positive impact of such solutions on sustainability and ecological well-being.

Tailored strategies should be developed for different regions and bioeconomy themes to address specific barriers identified in those contexts, whether it be a lack of knowledge, legislative hurdles, or technical capacity. Additionally, it is essential to distinguish between adopters and non-adopters, as their perceptions of barriers differ significantly. Non-adopters may require more targeted support in terms of technical capacity and addressing legislative barriers, whereas adopters may benefit from enhanced knowledge and information dissemination about bio-based solutions.

By addressing these barriers and tailoring interventions to the needs of different groups, it is more likely that end-users in rural areas will be encouraged to adopt bio-based solutions, contributing to the growth and sustainability of the bioeconomy in these regions.

3.2.2.3 Driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions

End-users were asked to provide their opinion about the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions (Fig. 23). The highest percentage of the end-users agreed that driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions are long-term economic benefits (8 out of 10 the end-users surveyed agreed) and supplier/customer demand (about 7 out of 10 end-users surveyed agreed). In comparison, the highest percentage of the end-users disagreed that driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions are peer/community pressure (almost a third of the end-users surveyed disagreed) and regulatory framework/compliance (almost a fifth of the end-users surveyed disagreed).

Figure 23: Drivers of bio-based solutions adoption in rural areas (N=417)

A statistically significant difference between how the end-users in different RBP answered the question about the main drivers of bio-based solutions adoption was identified (Fig. 24). In the South-East RBP, the highest percentage of the end-users surveyed (six-sevenths) agreed that long-term economic benefits are an important driving factor

for the adoption of bio-based solutions, while the highest percentage of the end-users surveyed (4 out of 10) in this region disagreed that peer/community pressure is a driving factor to adopt bio-based solutions.

The experts' survey results complement end-users results. The experts agreed that the main driving factors of rural small-scale producers, and SMEs to adopt and/or develop bio-based solutions in the South-East RBP are demand and prices. Experts explained that if the prices of products are high enough to warrant investments and people can see this for the long term then they will invest, adopt and develop bio-based solutions. Another driving factor is knowledge and making sure that stakeholders know their options. Thirdly, environmental considerations are becoming a key driving factor in many sectors (both for producers and consumers) and this becomes a driving change.

The highest percentage of the adopters surveyed in the North-East RBP (six-sevenths) and in the South-West RBP (four-fifths) agreed that long-term economic benefits are an important driving factor for bio-based solutions (Fig. 24).

According to the experts' survey results, the main driving factors of rural small-scale producers, and SMEs to adopt and/or develop bio-based solutions in the North-East RBP are motivation and personal initiative of entrepreneurs, financial support, informational support, qualified human resources. Very important remains the connection between creators of innovation as scientists and adopters as businesses. Competitiveness and production economics are driving factors not only for big producers but especially for small ones. Costs of production (must be lower than now compared with mass production), and country economy level provide not only production opportunities but also a demand. Higher income allows to select more expensive products, and searching for market opportunities leads to new markets and new products.

In the same vein, with peer/community pressure as a driving factor to adopt bio-based solutions most strongly disagreed the adopters surveyed in the North-East RBP (about a fifth), the South-West RBP (around a quarter), and the North-West RBP (two-fifths). The exception is the adopters surveyed in the North-West RBP that most strongly agreed that meeting sustainability targets is the main driver for the adoption of bio-based solutions (three quarters).

The experts have highlighted that in the North-West RBP are regulations and costs as well as the demand for bio-based solutions (products and services). Many governments provide incentives, subsidies, and grants to encourage the adoption of bio-based solutions. These policies can offset the costs of transitioning to new technologies and provide a competitive edge to rural SMEs. Moreover, stricter environmental regulations and standards often push businesses to find more sustainable alternatives. Bio-based solutions, which are generally considered more environmentally friendly, can help businesses meet compliance requirements.

Furthermore, experts have agreed that the demand for bio-based solutions (products and services) is playing a key role in deciding on the adoption of bio-based solutions. There is an increasing consumer demand for eco-friendly and sustainable products. Bio-based solutions cater to this demand, providing a marketing advantage for businesses that emphasise their commitment to environmental responsibility.

What are the main driving factors for adoption of bio-based solutions?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 24: Drivers of bio-based solutions adoption by regional RBP (N=417)

Moreover, experts have highlighted the importance of the involvement of local communities and other stakeholders through different communication messages and channels to transfer knowledge and to create a joint understanding of the opportunities for inclusive and sustainable bio-based solutions for the rural economy. Local communities, stakeholders, and organisations. This engagement can foster a sense of ownership and pride, leading to more sustainable and socially inclusive development.

The expert survey results have demonstrated that the main driving factor is customers who are increasingly demanding sustainable products and a growing environmental awareness among entrepreneurs to adopt circular and bio-based solutions.

To investigate the differences in the perceptions of the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions, we looked at them according to the end-users businesses' structural characteristics and remoteness of rural areas (Fig. 25).

*** Significant at p<0.01; ** significant at p<0.05; * significant at p<0.1.

Figure 25: Drivers of bio-based solutions adoption by the end-users businesses' structural characteristics and remoteness of rural areas (N=417)

In several of the driving factors listed, there were statistically significant differences in perception between end-users. At the bioeconomy theme level, about 8 out of 10 end-users surveyed in biomaterials/bio-based products agreed that environmental reasons/benefits/welfare is a driving factor to adopt bio-based solutions, whereas only

slightly less than half of the end-users surveyed in bioenergy agreed with that. An interesting finding is that even 4 out of 10 end-users surveyed are unsure whether environmental reasons/benefits/welfare is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions.

Two-thirds of legal entities and more than half of natural persons agreed that being an innovator is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions, whereas a fifth of legal entities and about a third of natural persons were unsure about that. A similar distribution of percentages was in terms of technical reasons. At the size of the farm/enterprise level, slightly more than two-thirds of the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises (less than two-thirds of the micro farms/enterprises) agreed that competitiveness is a driver to adopt bio-based solutions, slightly more than a fifth were unsure (a fourth of the micro farms/enterprises), and less than a tenth (about 15% of the micro farms/enterprises) disagreed with that. In terms of experience, about 8 out of 10 end-users surveyed with 11-15 years of experience agreed that financial incentive is a driver to adopt bio-based solutions.

Across adopters and non-adopters, statistically significant differences were found in perception between driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions that were based on meeting sustainability targets, long-term economic benefits, and supporting a local/circular economy. Both adopters and non-adopters surveyed (around 8 out of 10) most strongly agreed that long-term economic benefits are the main driver for the adoption of bio-based solutions.

At the remoteness of rural areas level, a higher percentage of the end-users surveyed from rural areas close to a city (in comparison to the end-users surveyed from remote rural areas) both agreed (about half) and disagreed (less than a fifth) that diversification of operations is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions.

In several of the driving factors listed in this question, there were statistically significant differences in the end-users' perception according to education level (Fig. 26).

Figure 26: Drivers of bio-based solutions adoption by the end-users education levels (N=417)

The greatest differences between the end-users with different level of education perceptions were based on supplier/customer demand, being an innovator, and technical reasons. Around three quarters of the end-users

surveyed with intermediate or higher education level agreed that supplier/customer demand is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions, while only less than half of the end-users surveyed with basic education agreed with this statement. Similarly, in comparison with the end-users surveyed who have a basic education level, a higher percentage of the end-users surveyed with intermediate or higher education agreed with long-term economic benefits, being an innovator, and technical reasons as the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions. The lowest percentage of the end-users surveyed with intermediate education agreed that peer/community pressure (about a third) and competitiveness (slightly more than half) are the drivers of bio-based solutions.

Adopting and developing bio-based solutions in each RBP requires a combination of technical, organisational, and strategic capacities. According to experts' survey results, these capacities enable businesses, communities, and individuals to navigate challenges and harness opportunities related to bio-based solutions. Following experts, comments, here are some **key capacities that are particularly important or all the RBP regions:**

- **Collaboration and Networking.** Part of the existing problems, according to experts, could be solved by participating in cooperation (marketing and advertising).
- **Regulatory and Policy Knowledge.** These capacities are crucial for the successful adoption and development of bio-based solutions in rural regions. Understanding and navigating the regulatory landscape and policy framework can have a significant impact on the feasibility, implementation, and sustainability of bio-based projects.
- **Financial Management and Funding Access.** Professionals with these capacities can identify and pursue various funding opportunities, such as government grants, private-sector investments, venture capital, and philanthropic support. They can match funding sources with the specific needs of the innovations.
- **Access to Resources and Infrastructure.** These capacities help to assess the Access to a consistent and sustainable Biomass Feedstock, land availability which is making it easier to establish biomass cultivation and production facilities, also transport, energy infrastructure, etc.
- **Appropriate education.** To apply sustainable bio-based solutions, appropriate education, economic knowledge about business plan, costs, marketing are necessary.

Based on the end-users opinions, a specific recommendation is to prioritise strategies that highlight the long-term economic benefits and respond to supplier/customer demand when promoting bio-based solutions in rural areas. These factors are recognised as key drivers for adoption. Additionally, while peer/community pressure and regulatory framework/compliance may not be the primary motivators, it's important to consider them as complementary elements in the adoption strategy, as they still hold significance for certain segments of the rural population.

End-users indicated consumer/customer demand as one of the most significant factors. Therefore, the end-users were asked their opinion/experience what factors are the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products (Fig. 27).

In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products?

Figure 27: End-users' perception of the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products (N=417)

The end-users surveyed most strongly agreed with the statements “too high price of bio-based products” (7 out of 10 end-users) and “lack of customer knowledge on quality benefits of bio-based products” (two-thirds of responses). The end-users surveyed most strongly disagreed with the statements “surplus of on-the-market products” and “uncertainty regarding sustainability of bio-based products” (4 out of 10 end-users). One important point to consider is that there is large uncertainty regarding the statement “too small market to cover demand if it grows fast”. The opinions are very split.

One of the most marked statistically significant differences in the opinions about the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products are in the RBP regions (Fig. 28). About two-fifths of the end-users surveyed in the South-East RBP said that they were unsure, only one fifth disagreed and about two-fifths agreed with the statement “uncertainty regarding the sustainability of bio-based products”, while the distribution of the responses to this statement in the other RBPs is very similar. Even half of the end-users surveyed in the South-East RBP disagreed that “surplus of on-the-market products” is the main barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products, whereas about 32-43% of the end-users surveyed in the other RBPs disagreed with this statement. There were almost a third of the end-users surveyed who agreed and the same percentage of the end-users surveyed who disagreed with this statement in the North-West RBP.

In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at p<0.01; ** significant at p<0.05; * significant at p<0.1.

Figure 28: End-users' perception of the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products by regional RBP (N=417)

According to experts, the growth of demand for biomaterials, bio-based products, and bioenergy products can be hindered by various factors. According to the experts' survey results in the South-East RBP, the main obstacles to increasing the demand are efforts needed to address “ecological limits” of biomass and to make consumption patterns more sustainable, also, lack of know-how, lack of funding, and cost efficiency solutions.

Between 55% (in the North-East RBP) and 77% (in the South-West RBP) of the end-users surveyed agreed that lack of customer knowledge on quality benefits of bio-based products is an important barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products. There were big differences (from 28% to 51%) in responses of the end-users surveyed who said that too small market to cover demand if it grows fast is an important barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products. There were no marked statistically significant differences in the results of the end-users opinions about the statement “too high price of bio-based products”.

According to the experts’ survey results in the North-East region, the main obstacles to the increase in demand are the lack of information, poor availability of the products themselves, alternative non-biobased solutions that are well available and aggressively promoted by the big suppliers of these solutions, the high price of bioproducts and low paying capacity of the population. In general, it can be said that it is the standard of living - the higher the standard of living, the more attention is paid to ecological and environmentally friendly solutions. Technologies, processes, insufficient market demand are some of the most important barriers. Inappropriate requirements in regulatory acts, bureaucratic obstacles must be changed for increasing demand for biomaterials, bio-based products, and bioenergy products.

According to the experts, these factors can vary depending on the specific sector in the North-West region, but here are some common barriers that can impact the demand for these bio-based solutions. The growth of bio-based industries often requires significant investment in research, development, and infrastructure. Shortage of Investment and Funding and limited access to funding can slow down expansion as well as the uncertain regulatory environment and unclear or inconsistent regulations and standards for biomaterials, bio-based products, and bioenergy products can create uncertainty and hinder market development. Moreover, experts have highlighted the importance of standardisation, inconsistent quality, and performance issues. If biomaterials or bio-based products do not match the quality and performance of traditional products, potential users may be hesitant to switch. Ensuring consistent quality and performance is essential to overcoming this barrier.

Experts have highlighted that in the South-West region, the lack of information and capacities are the main barrier to the growth of demand for biomaterials, bio-based products, and bioenergy products. The same was said about the demonstration of the performance of bio-based products in comparison with conventional products. These product prices may also be a barrier. Experts explained that still a lot of research is needed to replace many non-biological chemicals such as pesticides.

At the bioeconomy theme level, statistically significant differences in the opinions about the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products were found (Fig. 29). The highest percentage of the end-users surveyed in all bioeconomy themes agreed that lack of customer knowledge on quality benefits of bio-based products is the main barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products (about 57-71%). In comparison, about 22-36% and 21-48% of the end-users surveyed agreed that the surplus of on-the-market products and uncertainty regarding the sustainability of bio-based products, respectively, are the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products.

Statistically significant differences in the opinions about the main barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products were detected between the adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions (Fig. 30). The highest difference between the responses of the adopters and non-adopters surveyed (about a third of the adopters and about half of the non-adopters disagreed; 4 out of 10 adopters and almost a quarter of the non-adopters agreed) is related to the statement “uncertainty regarding the sustainability of bio-based products”. About five-sevenths of the adopters and two-thirds of the non-adopters surveyed agreed that “lack of customer knowledge on quality benefits of bio-based products” is an important barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products. Similarly, almost 8 out of 10 adopters and about 7 out of 10 non-adopters surveyed agreed that “too high price of bio-based products” is the barrier to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products.

In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 29: End-users' perception of the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products by bio-economy themes (N=417)

In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

Figure 30: End-users' perception of the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products by the adoption of bio-based solution (N=417)

According to the expert's survey results, the price of bio-based products is an important barrier. In general, bioproducts tend to be more expensive than the fossil/non-renewable equivalent. Producers prefer to keep the non-renewable to remain more competitive because consumers are largely unwilling to pay more for the new product. Moreover, experts have agreed that the level of produce, also consumers' awareness of the benefits and added value of bio-based products is one of the most important barriers. Therefore, they have to be trained indirectly, through different communication measures linked to sustainability circularity, the importance of labelling etc. Also, policy measures should help sustainable products to emerge.

In summary, addressing these barriers to customer demand growth for bio-based products requires a comprehensive approach that involves price optimisation, educational efforts, market analysis, sustainability assurance, and

effective surplus management. By proactively tackling these challenges, it is more likely that the demand for bio-based products will increase, fostering the growth of the bioeconomy and sustainable consumer choices. To effectively promote the growth of customer demand for bio-based products in different regions, it is essential to develop tailored strategies that address specific barriers, such as sustainability concerns, price competitiveness, and consumer education, in order to enhance awareness and adoption among end-users.

3.2.3 Needs, ideas and interests to adopt bio-based solutions

End-users had to answer the question about their specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution. About 70-80% of the end-users surveyed agreed with all six listed specific needs (Fig. 31). Here, only less than a tenth of the end-users surveyed disagreed with the listed specific needs.

Figure 31: End-users' specific needs to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in rural areas (N=417)

A statistically significant difference was found between how the end-users from different RBPs answered the question about the specific needs to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution (Fig. 32). Across regional RBPs, the largest percentage of the end-users surveyed (about six-sevenths) in the South-East RBP agreed with superior quality of bio-based solutions as a specific need to choose innovative small-scale bio-based solution. The largest undecidedness (almost a third) about superior quality was in the North-West RBP. When asked about compatibility with existing processes, the largest proportion of the end-users surveyed (almost 8 out of 10) in the South-West RBP agreed with that as a specific need.

Across regional RBPs, the largest percentage of the end-users surveyed (about six-sevenths) in the South-West RBP agreed with superior environmental performance as a specific need to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution. The largest undecidedness (around a fifth) about superior environmental performance was in the North-West and North-East RBPs. With the listed item “use for locally sourced feedstocks” as a specific need agreed about 87% of the end-users surveyed in the South-East RBP, whereas about a tenth of the end-users surveyed in the North-East RBP disagreed with this.

There were very different opinions about the coverage of customers’ need for bio-based solutions as a specific need: around four-fifths of the end-users surveyed in the South-East and North-East RBPs agreed with that, while around 6 out of 10 end-users surveyed in the South-West and North-West RBPs agreed with this listed specific need. The largest undecidedness (around a third) about the coverage of customers’ need for bio-based solutions was in the South-West and North-West RBPs.

What are your specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 32: End-users' specific needs to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution by regional RBP (N=417)

The expert's survey results have highlighted the fact that choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in the region, varies based on the specific context, and industry of the country, but here are some key factors to consider which has no significant differences across the RBPs. Furthermore, there are some common needs to consider, such as knowledge of Market Demand and Viability, as well as Regulatory and Policy Compliance; understanding of the regulatory environment and standards related to the chosen bio-based solution; ensuring that the solution complies with relevant regulations and permits for production, processing, and distribution.

Experts have mentioned that the lighthouse examples and decision support systems assess different alternatives and multicriteria indicators of circularity, environmental impact, social economic impact, and bio-based solutions viability.

According to the experts, choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in rural region a lot depends on society's needs, and when choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution, small-scale producers and SMEs need to consider technical feasibility, cost-effectiveness, market demand, product sustainability, access to financing, and R&D support. Energy intensity, waste management, water consumption, environmental impact issues could play a key role in this matter.

To investigate the differences in the perceptions about the specific needs to choose an alternative small-scale bio-based solution, we looked at them according to the end-users businesses' structural characteristics. In several of the specific needs listed, there were statistically significant differences in perception between the end-users (Fig. 33). At the bioeconomy theme level, around 81% and 84% of the end-users surveyed in food and agriculture, and bioenergy, respectively, agreed that superior cost-competitive products are a specific need when it comes to choosing an alternative small-scale bio-based solution, while around two-thirds of the end-users surveyed in

biomaterials/bio-based products, water systems, and forestry and natural habitats agreed with that. An interesting finding is that even one third of the end-users surveyed in bioenergy were unsure whether superior environmental performance is a specific need. In general, the answers to this item of the question are statistically significantly different.

There are statistically significant differences by legal form. About 72% of legal entities and 73% of natural persons agreed that superior quality of bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution, whereas 17% of legal entities and about 21% of natural persons were unsure about that. A similar distribution of percentages was in terms of superior environmental performance. About 7 out of 10 small and medium-sized farms/enterprises (almost 68% of the micro farms/enterprises) agreed that coverage of customers need for bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution, about 20% were unsure (about 23% of the micro farms/enterprises), and about 3% (almost a tenth of the micro farms/enterprises) disagreed with this listed need.

Across adopters and non-adopters, a statistically significant difference was found in the perception of two specific needs. About three quarters of the non-adopters (around two-thirds of the adopters) surveyed agreed that superior quality of bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution. Similarly, three quarters of the non-adopters (six-sevenths of the adopters) surveyed agreed that compatibility with existing processes is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution.

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 33: End-users' specific needs to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution by the end-users' businesses structural characteristics (N=417)

Considering the end-users specific needs when choosing innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas, it is clear that superior quality, compatibility with existing processes, superior environmental performance, use of locally sourced feedstocks, and coverage of customers’ needs are highly valued by a significant majority of end-users across different regions. Moreover, it is essential to prioritise these aspects in the development and marketing of such solutions. Additionally, efforts should be made to address the undecided or less enthusiastic responses, especially in regions where these specific needs may require more attention or awareness-building efforts.

When asked if the end-users’ farm or enterprise need support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions, three quarters of the end-users surveyed said “yes” (Fig. 34). The largest proportion (about 80%) of the end-users surveyed answered that they need financial and advisory support. The answers of the end-users surveyed statistically significantly differed based on regional RBPs. Across RBPs, about 8 out of 10 end-users surveyed in the South-East, North-East, and South-West RBPs said that they need support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions, while only about half of the end-users surveyed in the North-West RBP said they need support.

Figure 34: End-users' need for support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions in rural areas (N=417)

Statistically significant differences are found between how the end-users surveyed with different socio-demographic and business structural characteristics indicated the kind of support they would seek if they wanted to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions (Fig. 35). Most end-users (61-64%) from the South-East, North-East, and South-West RBPs would need training support. In contrast, only 15% of the end-users surveyed in the North-West RBP indicated this. It is interesting to note that the same patterns in differences between the opinions of the end-users from different RBPs were found for financial support – 78-88% of the end-users surveyed from the South-East, North-East, and South-West RBPs would need financial support, whereas only about half of the end-users surveyed from the North-West RBP said this. Another interesting finding is that about 7 out of 10 end-users surveyed from the North-East RBP would need research support, while about half of the end-users surveyed in the other RBPs said that they need this support.

Natural persons would need training and advisory support (64% and 86% of respondents, respectively), whereas these kinds of support probably seemed less useful for legal entities (50% and 72% of respondents, respectively). In contrast, research seemed to be more useful for legal entities (about two-thirds) and less useful for natural persons (about half). Not surprisingly, research support seemed to be less useful for the end-users surveyed with a basic education level (about a quarter) than for the end-users surveyed with intermediate or advanced education levels (about 6 out of 10). In the same vein, training support seemed to be more useful for the end-users surveyed with basic and intermediate education levels (about 90%) than for the end-users surveyed with advanced education level (72%).

Small and medium-sized farms/enterprises would need research support (7 out of 10), whereas this support probably seemed less useful for the farms/enterprises (slightly more than half). In contrast, training seemed to be more useful for the micro farms/enterprises (about 6 out of 10) and less useful for the small and medium-sized farms/enterprises (about half). Differences in the way adopters and non-adopters answered the question are also statistically

significant. The adopters surveyed were more likely to say they needed training and advisory support (63% and 89%, respectively). In contrast, about half of the non-adopters surveyed said they need training and 7 out of 10 non-adopters surveyed said they need advisory support.

If your answer is yes, please specify what kind of support would you seek?

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 35: End-users' need for support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions by socio-demographic and businesses structural characteristics (N=417)

At the bioeconomy theme level, the lowest proportions of the end-users surveyed in biomaterials/bio-based products and water systems would need training (36% and 41%, respectively) and advisory (56% and 64%, respectively) support. In bioenergy, forestry and natural habitats, and food and agriculture, 52-61% of the end-users surveyed selected training and 68-87% of the end-users surveyed selected advisory support they would seek if they wanted

to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions. At localisation (remoteness) level, training (two thirds of the end-users surveyed) and financial (9 out of 10 end-users surveyed) support seemed to be more useful for farms/enterprises from remote rural areas.

To better understand the advisory needs the experts have been asked do they think the advisory/brokerage services are well developed to support adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions and what kind of advice they may need the most. The survey has shown that the advisory and brokerage services related to bio-based solutions in rural region are developing to varying degrees across different countries and regions, and it may depend on factors such as government support, industry demand, and the presence of research institutions and innovation hubs. In terms of advice that adopters and non-adopters might need, several areas stand out. For example, technology assessment and feasibility of adopting specific bio-based technologies and solutions based on their resources, capabilities, and market conditions. Also, supply chain management, market analysis and business planning, i.e. understanding market trends, consumer preferences, and competitive landscapes is crucial. According to the experts, advisory services can assist in developing robust business plans/business models that outline market entry strategies, target segments, pricing strategies, and revenue projections. Moreover, the advisory services on Policy Advocacy and Government Support are crucial.

Moreover, in some regions (e.g. North-West and South-East RBP) the importance of the consultative potential of scientific institutions and research involving fulfilment by academic institutions have been highlighted. Technical advice, business development advice, cooperation questions, and the creation of innovative products are areas where academic and technical advisory and brokerage services are needed.

The experts agree that the advisory and brokerage services related to bio-based solutions in rural regions are poorly developed. Such services in the regions might be improved focusing on the factors such as the needs for assessing the real technological potential in the regions as well as assuring necessary technological transfer to the adopters. Advisory/mediation services should include technical support, training, and education, as well as finding necessary funding.

Moreover, the needs of collaborative platforms that connect rural businesses were mentioned for several times, research institutions, and industry experts should serve as hubs for knowledge sharing, networking, and cooperative projects and encourage active participation to stimulate innovation, foster partnerships, and drive the growth of the bio-based sector.

As mentioned above, financial support was indicated as the most important need for adopting bio-solutions. Therefore, we asked non-adopters a specific question of whether they would adopt any bio-based solution if it were supported through subsidies (Fig. 36). 7 out of 10 of them would begin to adopt a bio-based solution in the case of subsidising. We also asked non-adopters whether they would adopt any bio-based solution if they could cooperate and share the costs with others. Half of them answered yes.

Figure 36: Non-adopters' intentions to apply of a bio-based solution (N=136)

Non-adopters were also asked to indicate what kind of information they would need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution (Fig. 37). The highest share of them (8 out of 10) agreed that a cost-benefit model to reflect the bio-based activity specifics is an important kind of information before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution. Regarding the other kinds of information needed before making a decision to adopt any bio-based solution, about 7 out of 10 of the non-adopters surveyed agreed.

What kind of information would you need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution?

Figure 37: End-users' perception of the information they need before making a decision on any biological decision (N=136)

At the RBPs level, statistically significant differences were found between the opinions of the non-adopters surveyed on three kinds of information listed in this question (Fig. 38). About 7 out of 10 non-adopters surveyed in the South-East and South-West RBPs agreed that demonstration is needed before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution, while the highest percentage of the non-adopters surveyed (a fifth) in the North-East RBP disagreed with that. Similarly, the highest percentage of the non-adopters surveyed in the North-West RBP disagreed with peer-to-peer conversations with adopters and consultation with an official advisor (about 26% and 21% of the non-adopters surveyed, respectively) as the kinds of information needed before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution. Five-sixths (the highest percentage) of the non-adopters surveyed in the South-West RBP and two-fifths (the lowest percentage) of the non-adopters surveyed in the North-East RBP agreed with peer-to-peer conversations with adopter as a needed kind of information before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution. About 8 out of 10 non-adopters surveyed in the South-East and South-West RBPs agreed with consultation with an official advisor as a needed kind of information before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution, while only less than half of the non-adopters surveyed in the North-East and North-West RBPs respectively agreed with this kind of needed information.

What kind of information would you need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

Figure 38: End-users' perception of the information they need before making a decision on any biological decision regional RBP (N=136)

There are statistically significant differences between the perceptions of the non-adopters surveyed on the kind of information needed before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution by businesses' structural characteristics (Fig. 39). At the bioeconomy theme level, the highest percentage of the non-adopters surveyed agreed with the

consultation with the official advisor as needed information before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution among bioeconomy themes in bioenergy (three quarters) and food and agriculture (about four-fifths). In biomaterials, water systems, and forestry and habitats, 0%, 40% and about 48%, respectively, agreed with this statement. With “cost-benefit model to reflect the bio-based activity specifics” agreed 100%, 80%, and about 74% of the non-adopters surveyed in biomaterials, water systems, and food and agriculture, respectively, while only about 38% of the non-adopters surveyed agreed with that in bioenergy.

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 39: Non-adopters' perception of the information they need before making a decision on any biological solution by businesses structural characteristics (N=136)

The non-adopters' perception of the cost-benefit model to reflect the bio-based activity specifics as information needed before making a decision to adopt any bio-based solution is statistically significantly different between the non-adopters with different levels of experience. The largest proportion of the non-adopters surveyed (almost 90%) who selected this information are non-adopters with more than 16 years of experience.

There is also a statistically significant difference between the perceptions of the non-adopters surveyed in terms of legal form. About 62% of legal entities, compared to 76% of natural persons, chose peer-to-peer conversations with adopter as the kind of information they would need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution.

According to the expert's survey results, for both adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions in the rural region, there is a range of important information that can guide decision-making and understanding of these solutions. This information accounts economic issues (costs, sales opportunities and price, market demand), environmental issues and their solutions, good practice examples, dissemination of them through various channels, consumer attitude. Both adopters and non-adopters must know information about the benefits of bio-based solutions,

types, raw materials, production process, requirements of product quality, regulatory landscape, and possibilities to get financing support.

According to experts, this information can be obtained from an active scanning of innovative bio-based products and open discussion channels with current and potential suppliers, applying a systematic approach to incorporate bio-based products into public procurement, dedicated training and knowledge sharing to identify and replicate best practices. Financial benefits, environmental benefits, improved production processes must be considered as well.

To decide bio-based solutions based on the preferences and needs of non-adopters it is recommended to customize the efforts to cater the varying needs and preferences of non-adopters based on factors such as regional location, bioeconomy theme, years of experience, and legal form. By providing targeted information and support in these areas, it is more likely that non-adopters will be encouraged to embrace bio-based solutions, contributing to the growth and sustainability of these practices in rural areas.

3.2.4 Accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas

Finally, we asked both end-users and experts to specify accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas (Fig. 40-41). The end-users surveyed most strongly agreed with the listed accelerators “economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries”, “incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based products and bioenergy”, and “incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions” (about 85%). In contrast, the end-users surveyed most strongly disagreed with the listed accelerators’ “surveys and research about bio-based solutions” (about 14%), and “legislation obliging the use of bio-based products and bioenergy products in applications which are proven to have environmental benefits” (about 12%)

The opinions of the end-users surveyed from different RBPs differed statistically significantly on this question in 11 out of 14 listed accelerators (Fig. 41). The end-users surveyed (about 9 out of 10) from both South-East and South-West RBPs most strongly agreed that incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions are an accelerator of innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas. Similarly, the end-users in the North-East and North-West RBPs most strongly agreed with the accelerator “economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries” (87%). An interesting finding is that, in almost all cases, the largest proportion of the end-users surveyed from the North-West RBP were unsure about the listed accelerators of innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas.

In order to investigate the differences in the perception of the accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas, we looked at them according to bioeconomy themes and the adoption of bio-based solution. For several of the accelerators listed, there is a statistically significant difference in the perceptions of the end-users surveyed (Fig. 42). At the bioeconomy theme level, about 71% (the largest proportion) of the end-users surveyed in water systems agreed that the decision-making process with the participation of the wider public is an accelerator of bio-based solutions in rural areas, while only about 29% of the end-users surveyed in bioenergy agreed with that. Similarly, almost 90% of the end-users surveyed in biomaterials/bio-based products agreed that peer-to-peer knowledge exchange is an accelerator of bio-based solutions in rural areas, while only about half of the end-users surveyed in bioenergy agreed with that.

Across adopters and non-adopters, a statistically significant difference is found in the perception of six listed accelerators. The adopters surveyed most strongly agreed that incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based and bioenergy products, and a clear certification and labelling regulation framework for bio-based products and packaging are the accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas. In the same vein, the non-adopters surveyed most strongly agreed that incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based and bioenergy products, and

communication and informative events about bio-based solutions are the accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas?

Figure 40: End-users opinion about accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas (N=417)

In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 41: End-users opinion about accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions by regional RBP (N=417)

In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 42: End-users opinion about accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions by bioeconomy themes and adoption of bio-based solution (N=417)

Statistically significant differences are found in how the end-users surveyed with different socio-demographic and business structural characteristics perceived the accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas (Fig. 43). Most natural persons and legal entities (about 80% of natural persons and around 88% of legal entities) perceived incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based and bioenergy products, and incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions as accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas. Similarly, when analysing the end-users by size of the farms/enterprises, both small-medium sized farms/enterprises and micro farms/enterprises most strongly agreed that educational material or training on bio-based solutions, and informative online resources, online portals, and networking platforms where information on bio-based solutions, their applications, and producers can be exchanged (perceived as such by 75-80% of small-medium sized farms/enterprises and around 68% of micro farms/enterprises, respectively) are accelerators of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

The end-users surveyed with all levels of education most strongly agreed that economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries is an accelerator of bio-based solutions in rural areas. However, the proportion of the end-users was different: around 85-90% of the end-users with advanced and intermediate education level agreed with this statement, whereas only about half of the end-users with basic education level agreed with that.

In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas?

Strongly disagree | Disagree | I am not sure | Agree | Strongly agree

*** Significant at $p < 0.01$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; * significant at $p < 0.1$.

Figure 43: End-users opinion about accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions by socio-demographic and businesses structural characteristics (N=417)

Summarising the experts opinion for the future about promoting the rural circular bioeconomy and enhancing the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas of the SE region requires policy and extension services, technology, and the development of value chains if all of these works together biobased solutions will be adopted in the long-run.

In the short run technological developments to progress and policy must be supportive. Promotion of this economy, financial and educational support, technical assistance are needed. Awareness, information, promoting best practices, enhance interest can help to facilitate the implementation of increased circulation bioeconomy principles and

entrepreneurs for a better start of applying bio-based solutions in their daily activities. Moreover, in a short time period dissemination of information about legal instruments, support schemes, technologies, product use could be the key factors. In long-time perspective preparation and implementation of strategies, training of human resources, attracting young motivated and well-trained people to rural areas, enabling them to produce final products might become essential.

Experts agree that it is essential to apply strategies for both short and long-term efforts. Short-term strategies should be related to awareness and education campaigns, pilot projects and demonstrations, capacity building, training and knowledge exchange including networking and collaboration. Furthermore, the long-term strategies should be focused on infrastructure development, sustainable finance mechanisms, research, and innovation investments, etc.

Experts also have been asked their opinion if the knowledge transfer system, the share of experience and replicability of innovative bio-based solutions are efficient and integrated (e.g., involving different types of stakeholders depending on their functional performance), etc., in order to foster the sustainable bio-based solutions in rural regions.

Most of the experts agreed that the knowledge transfer system in rural region needs to be improved. It is essential in the decision-making process, as well as in implementing the technologies. But according to experts' systems availability is poor. It lacks unified knowledge dissemination system. There is no information about potential products, their technologies, potential raw materials, economic evaluation. Many things are diluted. On the other hand, energy and material resources are still large but it should be analysed and considered to what extent it will be possible to use them. Decision-makers should cooperate and develop future activities together.

Experts agreed that the knowledge transfer system in rural region is not well developed, and it lacks a methodological approach and governance of it. Experts have mentioned that the knowledge transfer system is mostly developed at the macro level, but not at the regional. This is a very strong shortcoming in terms of the proactive development of bio-based solutions in rural regions.

Based on the strong agreement among end-users regarding key accelerators for the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas, it is recommended that policymakers and stakeholders prioritize and invest programs and support mechanisms to encourage producers, especially small-scale enterprises and rural businesses, to adopt bio-based solutions. These incentives can include grants, subsidies, and technical assistance to facilitate the transition to more sustainable practices. To complement these efforts, it is essential to engage in effective communication and education about the advantages of bio-based solutions and their positive impact on the environment and the local economy. While surveys and research are not seen as strong accelerators by end-users, they still play a crucial role in informing policymakers and stakeholders about the effectiveness and impact of bio-based solutions. Therefore, continued research and data collection should not be neglected. Additionally, while mandatory legislation may not be popular among end-users, it can still be considered where appropriate to drive the adoption of bio-based products in applications with proven environmental benefits, provided that it is done in a way that considers the unique circumstances of rural areas.

3.2.5 Socio-demographic and business structural characteristics of end-users affecting the adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas

The data of the survey were analysed according to end-users' socio-demographic and business structural characteristics such as legal form of farm/enterprise, size of farm/enterprise, experience of farm/enterprise, bioeconomy sector, remoteness, education etc. The chi-square test was used to test for differences between the groups of end-users according to their socio-demographic and business structural characteristics. The results of the chi-square test show that these characteristics may have and do have an impact on the decisions and perceptions of the end-users.

In terms of economic activity by bioeconomy sectors/themes:

- The end-users in biomaterials and bioenergy sectors are more likely to adopt bio-based products and technologies than those in the other bioeconomy sectors.
- Easy replicable practice and positive legislative framework to switch to bio-based solutions are more important incentives to become an adopter of bio-based solutions for farms/enterprises in forestry and natural habitats, and in food and agriculture as well than in other bioeconomy sectors, while economic benefit is a more important incentive for farms/enterprises in bioenergy and food and agriculture as well.
- The end-users in bioenergy and food and agriculture were the most likely to agree that consultation with an official advisor is the kind of information needed before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution. The end-users in biomaterials and food and agriculture were the most likely to agree that the cost-benefit model to reflect the bio-based activity specifics is the kind of information needed before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution.
- Lack of knowledge is the most common barrier for end-users in food and agriculture, as well as forestry and natural habitats.
- The end-users in bioenergy and food and agriculture sectors most strongly agreed that superior cost-competitiveness products are needed when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution. In terms of superior environmental performance, the end-users from biomaterials and food and agriculture sectors most strongly agreed that there is a specific need to choose a bio-based solution.
- Training and advisory support are the most needed to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions for the end-users in food and agriculture, forestry and natural habitats, and bioenergy as well.
- The end-users from water systems most strongly agreed that the decision-making process with the participation of the wider public is an accelerator of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions, while the end-users from the biomaterials sector most strongly agreed that peer-to-peer knowledge exchange is an accelerator of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions.

In terms of the remoteness of rural areas:

- The end-users from rural areas close to a city are more likely to adopt innovative bio-based products as well as to operate at a village scale than those from remote rural areas than those from remote rural areas.
- The end-users from rural areas close to a city are more engaged with customers, researchers, authority of legislators, and their own employees than those from remote rural areas, while the end-users in remote rural areas are more engaged with other stakeholders.
- Government subsidies and/or other support schemes are incentives to become an adopter for a higher number of farms/enterprises from remote rural areas than those from rural areas close to a city.
- The end-users from remote rural areas, in contrast to those from rural areas close to a city, agreed more strongly that insufficient consumer interests/awareness and uncertainty around environmental benefits are the barriers to adopting bio-based solutions.

- The end-users from remote areas close to a city more strongly agree that diversification of operations is a driver of bio-based solutions than those from remote rural areas.
- Training and financial support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions is more necessary for the end-users from remote rural areas than for those from rural areas close to a city.

In terms of adoption of innovative bio-based solutions (adopters v.v. non-adopters):

- The most common barriers for non-adopters to adopt bio-based solutions are technical capacity and legislative barriers, while for adopters they are the lack of knowledge and technical capacity.
- The adopters were more likely than the non-adopters to agree that uncertainty regarding sustainability and other factors are the barriers to the growth of customer demand for bio-based products.
- The non-adopters are more likely than the adopters to agree that meeting sustainability targets, long-term economic benefits, and supporting a local/circular economy are the drivers of bio-based solutions adoption.
- The non-adopters are more likely to agree that the superior quality of bio-based solutions in comparison to conventional solutions is the specific need to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution than the adopters, while the adopters are more likely to agree that compatible with existing processes is the specific need to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution than the non-adopters.
- There is a greater need for training and advice to help the adopters identify opportunities for bio-based solutions than for the non-adopters.
- The non-adopters are more likely than the adopters to agree that incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based and bioenergy products and other factors are accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solution.

In terms of education level:

- The initiatives to adopt innovative bio-based product is very low among the end-users with basic education compared to the end-users with intermediate and advanced education level.
- The end-users with basic education are not at all engaged with customers and researchers, while those with advanced education are the most engaged with customers and researchers.
- The end-users with advanced education are more likely than those with basic and intermediate education to agree that supplier/customer demand, long-term economic benefits and other factors are the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions.
- Training is the most needed support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions for end-users with intermediate education, while research support is the most needed for end-users with advanced education.
- The end-users with basic education level are most unsure whether decision making with the participation of the wider public, economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of the traditional industries, and specialised agricultural exhibitions, demo projects and showcases, cross visits are accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions.

In terms of the legal form of the farm enterprise:

- Legal entities are more optimistic than natural persons about the relevance of their innovative product/production process for society after 2030.
- Legal entities are more likely to adopt bio-based technologies than natural persons.
- Natural persons are more likely than legal entities to operate at farm/enterprise scale, while legal entities are more likely than natural persons to operate at specific industry in rural areas.
- Legal entities are more engaged with customers, suppliers, researchers, thematic networks, and their own employees than natural person, while natural persons are more engaged with other stakeholders.
- Natural persons more than legal entities agreed that peer-to-peer conversations with adopter is a kind of information needed before making a decision on any bio-based solution.

- For both legal entities and natural persons, lack of clear guidelines or lack of a national bioeconomy strategy in action and lack of knowledge are the most common barriers to adopting bio-based solutions.
- Legal entities are more likely than natural persons to agree that being an innovator and technical reasons are the drivers of bio-based solutions.
- Natural persons are more likely than legal entities to agree that the superior quality of bio-based solutions in comparison to conventional solutions is the need to choose an alternative small-scale bio-based solution, while legal entities are more likely to agree that superior environmental performance is the need to choose an alternative small-scale bio-based solution.
- Natural persons need more training and advisory support than legal entities, while legal entities need more research support than natural persons to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions.
- Legal entities are more likely than natural persons to agree that educational material and training on bio-based solutions, incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based and bioenergy products, and other factors are accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions. Natural persons are more likely than legal entities to agree that a clear certification and labelling regulation framework for bio-based products and packaging is an accelerator of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions.

In terms of years of experience:

- The end-users with over ten years of experience are more engaged with associations and their own employees than those with shorter experience.
- For end-users with over ten years' experience economic benefit is the main incentive to become an adopter, while for end-users with shorter experience, other incentives are the main ones to become adopters.
- End-users with over ten years of experience most strongly agree that financial incentive is a driver of bio-based solutions adoption.

In terms of size classes of farms/enterprises:

- Small and medium-sized end-users (with 10-249 persons employed) are more likely to adopt bio-based technologies than micro-sized end-users (with less than 10 persons employed).
- Small and medium-sized end-users are more engaged with suppliers and their employees, while micro-sized end-users are more engaged with associations.
- For the small and medium-sized end-users, economic benefit and competition with successful brand owners' companies that are already investing in bio-based alternatives are greater incentives to adopt bio-based solutions than for the micro-sized end-users.
- The competitiveness encourages small and medium-sized end-users to become adopters more than micro-sized.
- The small and medium-sized end-users more strongly agree that coverage of customers' needs for bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution than micro-sized end-users.
- Training support is more needed for micro-sized end-users, while research support is more needed for small and medium-sized end-users.
- Small and medium-sized end-users are more likely than micro-sized end-users to agree that the educational material and training on bio-based solutions, informative online resources, online portals, and networking platforms, surveys, and research about bio-based solutions are accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions.

4 Conclusions

Based on end-users and experts' surveys, this report provides an overview of the stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests to promote currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas in the EU with a particular focus on thirteen EU member states and North Macedonia. The surveys were conducted in each country and then summarised to present the status and/or approach of all countries in common and each RBP region (North-West RPB, South-West RBP, North-East RBP, South-East RBP). Summary findings present six areas of survey results.

Adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas

Two-thirds of the adopters surveyed use innovative bio-based products, a slightly smaller proportion of them adopt bio-based processes, and less than half of them apply bio-based technologies. Almost two-thirds of the non-adopters surveyed said that they would apply innovative bio-based products, just over half of them chose bio-based technology, and slightly less than half of them said that they would apply bio-based processes.

This can be explained by several contextual factors, e.g., the bio-based solutions through the use of innovative bio-products require less knowledge, time, and financial resources, and are more understandable and easier to manage than innovative bio-processes or technologies.

The end-users in biomaterials and bioenergy sectors are more likely to adopt bio-based products and bio-technologies than those in the other bioeconomy sectors. This is regular and can be explained by several contextual factors. The manufacturing of biomaterials is classified as high-tech/medium-high-tech/medium-low-tech economic activity, while the agro-food and wood-based sectors are classified as a low-tech economic activity. Bioenergetics, one can say, is a new economic activity in rural areas, and modern bioenergy is developed based on innovations.

Most end-user bio-based solutions operate at the farm/enterprise scale, and a small number are industry-specific in rural areas and at the community or village level. It can be assumed that, in many cases, the adoption of bio-based solutions is more based on the internal interests of the farm/company (primarily to obtain economic benefits for themselves), and is less inclusive and poorly oriented to the interests of the local community/rural development.

Most of the surveyed end-users expect that their innovative product/production process will remain relevant for society in the long term and will lead to sustainability. This suggests that most adopters focus on the long-term perspective when implementing innovative bio-based solutions. The lowest proportion of the end-users from the South-West RBP than from the South-East, North-East, and North-West RBPs, think that their innovative product/production process will be relevant for society after 2030. A higher proportion of legal entities than natural persons foresees when their innovative products/production processes will be relevant for society after 2030.

End-users work with stakeholders to make bio-based solutions more efficient and sustainable (renewable, inclusive, circular). More than half of them do this with customers, suppliers, researchers and outside advisors. End-users/adopters from the North-East RBP, compared to the other RBPs, had the highest level of engagement with stakeholders, such as customers, suppliers, researchers, external advisors, associations, and their own employees. This pattern may be correlated with the region-level specific since the largest proportion of the end-users surveyed were small and medium-sized legal entities in the North-East RBP.

According to socio-demographic and business structural characteristics, legal entities are more engaged with customers, suppliers, researchers, thematic networks and own employees than natural persons. End-users with over ten years of experience are the most engaged with associations and own employees than those with shorter experience. In contrast to end-users with higher education, end-users with a basic education have not had any engagement with customers and researchers. At the size of the farm/enterprise level, the majority of small and medium-sized end-users engaged with suppliers and own employees, while the majority of micro end-users engaged with

suppliers and associations. The end-users from rural areas close to a city had more engagement with customers, researchers, authority of legislators, and own employees than the end-users from remote regions. However, adopters from remote rural areas had more engagement with other stakeholders.

In expert opinion, small-scale bio-based solutions can be more successfully implemented when active and significant involvement with stakeholders exists. EU, national, regional, and local government institutions can be and should be active stakeholders, as well as cooperatives, agricultural/technical advisors, other producers/processors, and universities/research organisations, could be more active in the field as well.

Incentives to become adopters of bio-based solutions

Economic benefits and enhanced product performance and/or functionalities are the main incentives to become adopters of innovative bio-based solutions. The survey revealed that the economic benefit is the biggest incentive to apply innovative solutions in the bioenergy, forestry and agri-food sectors, and for end-user with more than ten years of experience. A replicable good practice is another important incentive to become an adopter in the agri-food sector, as well as in both forestry and water systems. Rural residents usually tend to implement the innovations that are already successful and therefore are more reliable and less risky for them. In the North-East RBP, the easily replicable good practice and economic benefit are the incentives that led them to become adopters. This makes this region different from other RBPs.

Government subsidies and/or other support schemes are incentives to become an adopter for more than half of end-users from remote rural areas, however, only for a third of end-users from rural areas close to a city. Every seventh end-user/non-adopter surveyed would begin to adopt an innovative bio-based solution if it were supported through subsidies. In addition, about half of the surveyed non-adopters would adopt any bio-based solution if they could cooperate and share the costs with others.

In experts perception, promoting the circular economy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas requires a multi-faceted approach that goes beyond economic incentives. A range of non-economic incentives such as capacity building, education, training, networking, and politics can play a crucial role in promoting the development and application of circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas. The experts agreed, that by combining these incentives, governments, organisations, and communities can create a supportive ecosystem that encourages the development and application of circular bioeconomy solutions in rural areas.

Barriers to the adoption of bio-based solutions

The survey revealed that a lack of financial capital is one of the main barriers to adopting innovative bio-based solutions. Meanwhile, almost two-thirds of end-users surveyed in the South-East and South-West RBPs, consider lack of knowledge as the main barrier to adopting innovative bio-based solutions. Meanwhile, in the North-East RBP, the highest share of the end-users surveyed agreed that lack of clear guidelines or there is not a national bioeconomy strategy in action is the main barrier to adopting bio-based solutions. In addition, more than half of the end-users surveyed in the North-West RBP think that legislative barriers are important to the adaptation of these solutions.

In addition, technical capacity and legislative barriers were rated by surveyed non-adopters as highly important barriers to adopting innovative bio-based solutions. In comparison, lack of knowledge and technical capacity were identified as the main barriers to adopting bio-based solutions by the adopters surveyed. It was found the largest differences between the perceptions of barriers by legal entities and natural persons were based on lack of knowledge, partnerships, clear guidelines or the absence of a national bioeconomy strategy, uncertainty about environmental benefits, uncertainties about the supply of feedstock or ingredient, incompatibility with existing processes or high replacement costs, higher life-cycle costs to buyers, and legislative barriers.

In experts opinion, the barriers vary depending on the specific context for the region, but here are some common challenges that adopters and non-adopters are facing. Those barriers are lack of skills and qualified personnel, insufficient and/or complex regulations, limited funding, and investment, knowledge gaps, poor infrastructure, lack of cooperation, and lack of good practice. According to the expert's survey results, membership with small produce groups, cooperatives, and similar organisations can indeed help both adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions overcome many of the challenges they face.

Driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions

The survey revealed that the main driving factors for the adoption of innovative bio-based solutions are long-term economic benefits and supplier/customer demand. Both adopters and non-adopters surveyed agree that long-term economic benefits are the main drivers. Similarly, end-users from the South-East, North-East and South-West RBPs are of the same opinion. Meanwhile, most end-users from the North-West RBP think that meeting sustainability targets is the main driver for the adoption of bio-based solutions. The end-users surveyed in the biomaterials sector agreed that environmental reasons/benefits/welfare is a driving factor to adopt bio-based solutions, while in other bioeconomy sectors up to half of end-users are unsure that this driving factor is so important.

Differences are found between how surveyed end-users with different socio-demographic and business structural characteristics indicated the driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions. For instance, compared to natural persons, a higher percentage of the legal entities agreed that being an innovator is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions. A much higher percentage of small and medium-sized end-users agreed that competitiveness is a driver to adopt bio-based solutions than very small end-users. A higher percentage of the end-users surveyed from rural areas close to a city (in comparison to those from remote rural areas) agreed that diversification of operations is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions. More than two-thirds of surveyed end-users with intermediate or higher education levels agreed that supplier/customer demand is a driving factor for the adoption of bio-based solutions, while less than half of end-users with basic education agreed with this statement. Similarly, in comparison with the end-users surveyed who have a basic education level, a higher percentage of the end-users surveyed with intermediate or higher education agreed with long-term economic benefits, being an innovator, and technical reasons as the main driving factors for the adoption of bio-based solutions.

Experts have agreed that the demand for biobased solutions (products and services) is playing a key role in deciding on the adoption of bio-based solutions. There is increasing consumer demand for eco-friendly and sustainable products. Bio-based solutions cater to this demand, providing a marketing advantage for businesses that emphasise their commitment to environmental responsibility. Adopting and developing bio-based solutions in each RBP requires a combination of technical, organisational, and strategic capacities.

Needs, ideas and interests to adopt bio-based solutions

Almost four out of five surveyed end-users agree that coverage of customers' needs for bio-based solutions, use for locally sourced feedstocks, superior environmental performance, compatibility with existing processes, cost-competitive products, and superior quality of bio-based solutions in comparison to conventional solutions are the specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution.

Differences are found in how the end-users with different socio-demographic and business structural characteristics indicated the specific needs to adopt bio-based solutions. For instance, four out of five end-users surveyed in agri-food and bioenergy sectors agreed that superior cost-competitive products are the main specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative small-scale bio-based solution, while up to two-thirds of end-users from biomaterials, water systems, and forestry sectors agreed with that. Natural persons slightly more than legal entities agreed that the superior quality of bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution. Natural persons slightly more than legal entities agreed that the superior quality of bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution. Compared to micro end-users, a higher percentage of small and

medium-sized end-users agreed that coverage of customers' needs for bio-based solutions is a specific need to choose an alternative bio-based solution. For higher proportion of the non-adopters compared to the adopters agreed that superior quality of bio-based solutions and compatibility with existing processes are specific needs to choose an alternative bio-based solution.

The experts' survey results have highlighted the fact that choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in the region varies based on the specific context, and industry of the country, but here are some key factors to consider which have no significant differences across the RBPs. Choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution in rural regions a lot depends on society's needs, and when choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution, small-scale producers and SMEs need to consider technical feasibility, cost-effectiveness, market demand, product sustainability, access to financing, and R&D support. Energy intensity, waste management, water consumption, and environmental impact issues could play a key role in this matter. Based on the preferences and needs of non-adopters before deciding to embrace bio-based solutions, it is recommended that efforts should be customised to cater to the varying needs and preferences of non-adopters based on factors such as regional location, economy theme, years of experience, and legal form.

Accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas

The survey of both experts and end-users revealed various accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. Most of the surveyed end-users think that economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries, incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based products and bioenergy, and incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions are accelerators of innovative small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. The end-users surveyed from both South-East and South-West RBPs most strongly agreed that incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions are an accelerator of innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas. Similarly, the end-users in the North-East and North-West RBPs most strongly agreed with the accelerators' like economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries.

In addition, experts agree that in a short time dissemination of information about legal instruments, support schemes, technologies, and product use could be the key factors for an acceleration of small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. From a time, perspective preparation and implementation of strategies, training of human resources, and attracting young motivated, and well-trained people to rural areas, enabling them to produce final products might become essential.

5 Recommendations

One of the overall ambitions of the survey was to gather insights from both end-users and experts in the field of bio-based solutions and adopters and non-adopters experiences, needs, ideas and interests. The survey results explored the current perceptions, challenges, and opportunities within these domains, with the ultimate goal of shaping the future of sustainable practices in various bioeconomy themes and agro-industries.

The survey helped to bridge the gap between end-users and experts, acknowledging that each group possesses valuable insights. End-users, who directly engage with bio-based products and circular economy practices, provide real-world feedback, while experts offer specialised knowledge and vision. By bringing these perspectives together, the survey has created a holistic understanding of the current landscape.

Moreover, the survey results have helped to identify not only the most replicable experiences but also challenges, barriers, describe the needs to better understand, develop and adopt bio-based solutions in different European regions. This information is crucial for identifying bottlenecks and areas for bio-based innovations and its support ecosystem. Therefore, the recommendations on how to foster successful adoption in the different European regions address the key factors that can play a crucial role in achieving these goals.

The survey's outcome recommendations are essential for various stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, agro-industry beginners and leaders, adopters and non-adopters, and environmental advocates. These recommendations will be based on a comprehensive analysis of survey responses, merging the practical insights of end-users with the strategic insights of experts. They will provide a roadmap for advancing bio-based solutions and circular bioeconomy practices.

In summary, the survey results serve as a vital tool for capturing the diverse perspectives of end-users and experts in the field. The resulting recommendations are crucial for guiding stakeholders toward more sustainable practices and fostering bio-based innovation in all five bioeconomy themes. The ultimate significance of these recommendations lies in their potential to drive sustainable growth and circular bioeconomy in different European regions.

Furthermore, by implementing the suggested strategies and best practices, agro-industries and governments can reduce their ecological footprint, minimise waste, and contribute to a more sustainable and resilient future.

Recommendations to foster bio-based innovations in European rural areas can be grouped into several categories to ensure a comprehensive approach to circular bioeconomy development. Here are some key groupings for these recommendations.

1. Awareness campaigns and training

Awareness campaigns: tailored to rural communities to build the skills and knowledge needed for bio-based businesses and circular practices in rural areas, and also to inform residents, farmers, and entrepreneurs about the benefits and opportunities of circular bioeconomy and bio-based solutions.

Skill Development Programs: implement training programs and workshops to equip rural residents with the skills required for bio-based industries, including biotechnology and sustainable agriculture including knowledge related to bio-based technologies and practices. It is useful to equip individuals with the necessary technical assistance and mentoring to individuals and organisations involved in bio-based projects and initiatives to ensure they have access to expert guidance.

Collaboration with Educational Institutions: partner with local schools, colleges, and universities to offer specialised courses and degrees related to bio-based technologies.

Knowledge Sharing: establish networks for knowledge sharing and mentorship, connecting rural innovators with experts in the field. The professional capacity can be increased when fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing networks among professionals in the bio-based industry, facilitating the exchange of best practices/lighthouses and lessons learned from practice.

Tailored incentive programs at the regional level: with a particular emphasis on promoting easily replicable good practices, positive frameworks for transitioning to bio-based solutions, government subsidies and support schemes, enhanced product performance, and economic benefits, as these were the most influential factors cited by adopters, thereby encouraging wider adoption and sustainability in rural regions.

Demonstrations that showcase in regions: it is crucial to demonstrate the practical applications and advantages of bio-based solutions, especially in regions where there is a higher demand for such demonstrations.

Effective communication and knowledge transfer: it is essential to engage in effective communication and education about the advantages of bio-based solutions and their positive impact on the environment and the local economy. While surveys and research are not seen as strong accelerators by end-users, they still play a crucial role in informing policymakers and stakeholders about the effectiveness and impact of bio-based solutions. Therefore, continued research and data collection should not be neglected. Additionally, while mandatory legislation may not be popular among end-users, it can still be considered where appropriate to drive the adoption of bio-based products in applications with proven environmental benefits, provided that it is done in a way that considers the unique circumstances of rural areas.

2. Policy and Regulatory Support

Incentives for Rural Entrepreneurs: create financial incentives, tax breaks, or grants for individuals and businesses in rural areas engaged in bio-based innovation. Dedicate funding through European Union (EU) programs, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Horizon Europe, for circular bioeconomy projects and rural bio-based solutions should be developed to help alleviate this obstacle, making it more financially feasible for farms and enterprises to transition to bio-based solutions.

Streamlined Regulatory Processes: simplify and expedite the permitting and regulatory processes for bio-based projects to encourage investment.

Clear and supportive regulatory frameworks: they encourage innovation and circular practices, organic agriculture, and agroecological approaches that contribute to circularity and socioeconomic sustainability and reduce environmental impact.

Supportive Legislation: enact policies that promote sustainable agriculture, forestry, and bio-based product manufacturing in rural regions.

Considered regional disparities: government subsidies and support schemes should be strategically targeted, with a focus on remote rural areas where they appear to be more influential.

Tailored interventions: to the needs of different groups, it is more likely that end-users in rural areas will be encouraged to adopt bio-based solutions, contributing to the growth and sustainability of the bioeconomy in these regions. It is important to develop programs and support mechanisms to encourage producers, especially small-scale enterprises and rural businesses, to adopt bio-based solutions. These incentives can include grants, subsidies, and technical assistance to facilitate the transition to more sustainable practices.

Tailored strategies: should be developed for different regions and bioeconomy themes to address specific barriers identified in those contexts, whether it be a lack of knowledge, legislative hurdles, or technical capacity. Additionally, it is essential to distinguish between adopters and non-adopters, as their perceptions of barriers differ significantly. Non-adopters may require more targeted support in terms of technical capacity and addressing legislative barriers, whereas adopters may benefit from enhanced knowledge and information dissemination about bio-based solutions. Those strategies aim to incentivise consumers to purchase sustainable bio-based products and bioenergy.

This could include awareness campaigns, labelling programs, and financial incentives that highlight the environmental and economic benefits of these products.

Financial Support and Access: improve access to financial resources for bio-based solution adoption by providing guidance and support in identifying suitable funding options. Create awareness about government grants, subsidies, and private-sector investments available for bio-based projects. Additionally, consider establishing local financial support mechanisms tailored to the unique needs of rural businesses and communities pursuing bio-based solutions. It is crucial to recognise that small businesses may have limited resources and capacity to adopt bio-based solutions. Therefore, it is important to provide financial incentives, grants, or subsidies to small businesses with fewer than 10 employees to help them meet the specific needs of their sectors.

Feedback mechanisms and evaluation systems: it is important to regularly assess and enhance the support ecosystem, ensuring it remains responsive to evolving needs and fosters sustainable bio-based solutions in rural areas and to track the adoption and impact of bio-based solutions in different sectors. Use this data to refine policies and support mechanisms accordingly. Also, it is important to encourage active participation and feedback from end-users and businesses in the development and implementation of bio-based solutions. Foster a sense of ownership and engagement among stakeholders.

2. Community Engagement and Collaboration

Collaborative Ecosystems: to develop collaborative platforms, research, and innovation hubs, that help to facilitate and transfer technology and knowledge from urban innovation centers to rural areas through outreach programs, technology parks, and partnerships with research institutions that focus on bio-based technologies, sustainable agriculture, and circular economy practices. These networks can facilitate cost-sharing and resource pooling among non-adopters, making it easier for them to collectively invest in and adopt bio-based solutions. Such initiatives can enhance the adoption rate and promote knowledge exchange among peers, driving the sustainable growth of bio-based solutions in rural communities.

Local Entrepreneurship Support: establish business incubators and mentorship programs to encourage local entrepreneurs to pursue bio-based ventures.

Facilitated engagement: promoted and facilitated engagement between adopters and stakeholders, particularly in regions with lower engagement, to enhance the sustainability, applicability, and replicability of bio-based solutions.

Multiactors approach: collaboration and partnership among government agencies, industry associations, research institutions, financial entities, NGOs, local communities, and other stakeholders to provide comprehensive support, resources, and incentives for small-scale producers in rural regions to transition towards bio-based production, thereby promoting sustainability and innovation in these areas.

Peer-to-peer conversations: these interactions between non-adopters and those who have already adopted bio-based solutions can help non-adopters gain insights from the experiences of others and address their concerns or doubts.

Advisory and brokerage services: the high-quality advisory services that meet the real technological potential in the regions as well as ensure necessary technological transfer to the adopters it is far from the real needs. Opportunities for non-adopters to consult with official advisors who can provide expert guidance and information about the feasibility and benefits of bio-based solutions, tailored to their specific circumstances.

3. Market Access and Promotion

Market analysis and forecasting: while some end-users may perceive market limitations, others see growth potential. Policymakers and industry stakeholders should conduct comprehensive market assessments to determine the actual potential and create strategies accordingly.

Sustainability standards and certifications: it is essential to ensure that bio-based products meet rigorous sustainability standards and certifications, providing consumers with confidence in their eco-friendliness. A favourable regulatory environment supports the production and adoption of bio-based solutions, ensuring quality and environmental performance standards are met. This includes incentives and tax breaks for businesses that invest in bio-based technologies.

Market demand: it is crucial to monitor production levels and market demand carefully. Effective inventory management and distribution strategies should be in place to prevent oversupply and waste.

Growth of customer demand in regions: it is essential to develop tailored strategies that address specific barriers, such as sustainability concerns, price competitiveness, and consumer education, in order to enhance awareness and adoption among end-users.

Market agreements: it is crucial to facilitate market access for bio-based products, both domestically and internationally. This includes trade agreements and initiatives to promote the export of bio-based products, especially those with superior quality and environmental performance.

4. Research and Development

Allocated resources for R&D: it is important to invest in research and development initiatives that focus on enhancing the quality and cost-competitiveness of bio-based products, particularly in the food and agriculture and bioenergy sectors, where these aspects are highly valued.

Technology transfer: it is recommended to invest in research initiatives and collaborative technology transfer platforms connecting rural businesses with research institutions to drive innovation and knowledge transfer.

Available tools and models: it is necessary to make available cost-benefit models that specifically reflect the unique aspects of bio-based activities. These models should help non-adopters understand the financial implications and benefits associated with adopting bio-based solutions.

6 References

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7 Annex I: Sampling frame by countries

Netherlands	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, biogas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	58.1%	24.5%	4.1%	0.3%	0.4%	12.2%	0.4%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in total bioeconomy turnover	15-16	6-7	1-2	0-1	0-1	3-4	1-2	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	7-8	10-11	1-2	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	45%		59%	n.d	n.d	54%	25%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	27%		14%	n.d	n.d	15%	28%	
Limited liability enterprise***	28%		27%	n.d	n.d	31%	47%	
Natural person****		91%						
Legal person****		9%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	80%	n.d	90%	n.d	n.d	87%	95%	
10 persons employed or more	20%	n.d	10%	n.d	n.d	13%	5%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bio-energy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 14: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Netherlands

France	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/ bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	56.1%	21.7%	4.1%	1.6%	0.6%	15.2%	0.7%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	14-15	5-6	1-2	1-2	0-1	4-5	0-1	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	7-8	9-10	1-2	3-4	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	33%		58%	n.d	n.d	59%	8%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	0%		0%	n.d	n.d	0%	1%	
Limited liability enterprise***	67%		42%	n.d	n.d	41%	92%	
Natural person****		59%						
Legal person****		30%						
Group holding****		11%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	90%	n.d	91%	n.d	n.d	92%	99%	
10 persons employed or more	10%	n.d	9%	n.d	n.d	8%	1%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 15: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for France

Germany	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	52%	12%	7.9%	1.2%	0.1%	22.2%	4.6%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	14-15	3-4	2-3	0-1	0-1	6-7	1-2	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	7-8	6-7	2-3	2-3	2-3	4-5	3-4	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	63%		65%	n.d	n.d	38%	53%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	16%		12%	n.d	n.d	16%	41%	
Limited liability enterprise***	22%		23%	n.d	n.d	45%	7%	
Natural person****		87%						
Legal person****		2%						
Group holding****		11%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	100%	n.d	100%	n.d	n.d	100%	100%	
10 persons employed or more	13%	n.d	33%	n.d	n.d	21%	87%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 16: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Germany

Denmark	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	50.6%	18.1%	4.2%	1%	1%	22.7%	2.4%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	13-14	5-6	1-2	0-1	0-1	6-7	1-2	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	6-7	9-10	1-2	2-3	2-3	3-4	3-4	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	27%		35%	n.d	n.d	25%	6%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	4%		1%	n.d	n.d	2%	44%	
Limited liability enterprise***	69%		64%	n.d	n.d	73%	50%	
Natural person****		91%						
Legal person****		8%						
Group holding****		1%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	64%	n.d	79%	n.d	n.d	74%	92%	
10 persons employed or more	36%	n.d	21%	n.d	n.d	26%	8%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 17: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Denmark

Spain	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	55.9%	23.5%	4.2%	0.8%	1.1%	13.8%	0.7%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	19-21	8-9	2-3	0-1	0-1	5-6	0-1	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	10-12	14-15	1-2	2-3	2-3	3-4	2-3	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	32%		41%	n.d	n.d	39%	7%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	13%		7%	n.d	n.d	5%	9%	
Limited liability enterprise***	55%		52%	n.d	n.d	56%	83%	
Natural person****		93%						
Legal person****		7%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	80%	n.d	90%	n.d	n.d	83%	97%	
10 persons employed or more	20%	n.d	10%	n.d	n.d	17%	3%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 18: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Spain

Portugal	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	41.5%	18%	10.8%	3.1%	1.5%	23.3%	1.8%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	14-15	6-7	3-5	1-2	1-2	8-9	1-2	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	7-8	11-12	3-4	3-5	3-5	4-5	3-4	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	40%		48%	n.d	n.d	41%	76%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	3%		0%	n.d	n.d	1%	1%	
Limited liability enterprise***	58%		52%	n.d	n.d	58%	23%	
Natural person****		94.5%						
Legal person****		5.3%						
Group holding****		0%						
Common land unit****		0.2%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	80%	n.d	90%	n.d	n.d	83%	97%	
10 persons employed or more	20%	n.d	10%	n.d	n.d	17%	3%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 19: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Portugal

Italy	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	44.6%	17.4%	7.1%	0.8%	0.5%	27.2%	2.4%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	15-16	5-6	3-4	0-1	0-1	10-12	1-2	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	8-9	11-12	2-4	2-3	2-3	6-7	3-4	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	42%		56%	n.d	n.d	43%	14%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	30%		24%	n.d	n.d	17%	12%	
Limited liability enterprise***	28%		21%	n.d	n.d	40%	74%	
Natural person****		98.3%						
Legal person****		1.4%						
Group holding****		0%						
Common land unit****		0.2%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	87%	n.d	93%	n.d	n.d	80%	96%	
10 persons employed or more	13%	n.d	7%	n.d	n.d	20%	4%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 20: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Italy

Latvia	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	25.2%	21.8%	28.5%	17.4%	1%	4.9%	1.2%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	8-9	7-8	10-12	6-7	0-1	2-3	1-2	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	3-4	8-9	7-8	11-12	2-3	1-2	2-4	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	26%		23%	60%	60%	36%	6%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	2%		1%	40%	40%	1%	4%	
Limited liability enterprise***	72%		76%		0%	63%	90%	
Natural person****		99%						
Legal person****		1%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	77%	n.d.	76%	n.d.	n.d.	88%	80%	
10 persons employed or more	23%	n.d.	24%	n.d.	n.d.	12%	20%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 21: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Latvia

Lithuania	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	36.2%	25.8%	20.3%	4.5%	1%	10.8%	1%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	12-13	8-10	7-8	2-3	0-1	4-5	1-2	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	6-7	13-15	4-5	4-5	2-3	2-3	3-4	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	51%		66%	n.d	n.d	69%	28%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	1%		0%	n.d	n.d	0%	0%	
Limited liability enterprise***	48%		34%	n.d	n.d	31%	72%	
Natural person****		99%						
Legal person****		1%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	78%	n.d	88%	n.d	n.d	89%	92%	
10 persons employed or more	22%	n.d	12%	n.d	n.d	11%	8%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 22: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Lithuania

Poland	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	52.9%	19.6%	11.5%	2.5%	0.1%	12.3%	1.1%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	18-19	7-8	4-5	1-2	0-1	3-5	1-2	34-42
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	9-10	12-13	3-4	4-5	2-3	2-3	2-4	34-42
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	34-42
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	76%		91%	n.d	n.d	82%	37%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	9%		2%	n.d	n.d	4%	6%	
Limited liability enterprise***	16%		6%	n.d	n.d	13%	57%	
Natural person****		99%						
Legal person****		1%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	73%	n.d	90%	n.d	n.d	84%	89%	
10 persons employed or more	27%	n.d	10%	n.d	n.d	16%	11%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 23: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Poland

Greece	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	48.2%	35.9%	1.9%	0.2%	2.6%	10.1%	1.1%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	12-13	9-10	1-2	0-1	1-2	2-3	0-1	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	6-7	12-13	1-2	1-2	3-4	1-2	2-3	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	58%		71%	n.d	n.d	57%	23%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	27%		19%	n.d	n.d	21%	47%	
Limited liability enterprise***	15%		10%	n.d	n.d	22%	30%	
Natural person****		99.8%						
Legal person****		0.2%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	89%	n.d	95%	n.d	n.d	87%	99%	
10 persons employed or more	11%	n.d	5%	n.d	n.d	13%	1%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 24: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Greece

Slovenia	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	31.3%	17.4%	14.7%	6.4%	0.2%	29.7%	0.3%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	8-9	4-5	4-5	2-3	0-1	8-9	0-1	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	4-5	8-9	3-4	5-6	1-2	4-5	1-2	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	73%		73%	n.d	n.d	51%	60%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	1%		1%	n.d	n.d	1%	1%	
Limited liability enterprise***	26%		26%	n.d	n.d	48%	39%	
Natural person****		99.6%						
Legal person****		0.4%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	93%	n.d	92%	98%	n.d	85%	97%	
10 persons employed or more	7%	n.d	8%	2%	n.d	15%	3%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 25: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Slovenia

North Macedonia	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	20.6%	60.8%	1%	2.1%	0.1%	15.4%	0%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	5-6	16-17	0-1	1-2	0-1	4-5	0	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	3-4	18-19	1-2	2-3	0-1	2-4	0-1	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	19%		9%	n.d	n.d	9%	0%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	0%		0%	n.d	n.d	0%	1%	
Limited liability enterprise***	80%		91%	n.d	n.d	91%	99%	
Natural person****		n.d						
Legal person****		n.d						
Group holding****		n.d						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	81%	n.d	88%	n.d	n.d	73%	91%	
10 persons employed or more	19%	n.d	12%	n.d	n.d	27%	9%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 26: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for North Macedonia

Romania	Food/agriculture		Forestry/natural habitats		Water systems	Bio-materials/bio-based products	Bioenergy	Total
	Food, beverage and tobacco	Agriculture	Wood products and furniture	Forestry	Fishery, aquaculture, aquatic	Biomaterials, biorefinery, bio-products	Bio-based electricity, bio-gas, etc.	
%Share in the total bioeconomy turnover in 2019	34.2%	38.2%	11%	3.9%	1%	11.2%	0.5%	100%
Approximate sample size for interviewing end-users (i.e., individuals or small-medium sized organisations/business entities)								
Approximate number of end-users for an interview in proportionally to %Share in the total bioeconomy turnover	9-10	10-11	3-4	1-2	0-1	3-4	0-1	26-33
Corrected approximate number of end-users for an interview*	4-5	12-13	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	2-3	26-33
Final approximate number of end-users for an interview corrected by the country's experts**	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	...-...	26-33
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the legal form (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Sole proprietorship***	29%		33%	n.d	n.d	21%	5%	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations, etc.***	1%		0%	n.d	n.d	1%	0%	
Limited liability enterprise***	71%		67%	n.d	n.d	78%	95%	
Natural person****		99%						
Legal person****		1%						
Group holding****		0%						
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by size class (by persons employed) (based on farm structure and business demography statistics by main kind of activity in the country, 2020)								
Up to 10 persons employed	84%	n.d	89%	n.d	n.d	81%	85%	
10 persons employed or more	16%	n.d	11%	n.d	n.d	19%	15%	
Approximate percentage distribution of interviewing end-users by the kind of production								
Only primary production of biological renewable raw materials and feedstocks (i.e., agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products)		50%		50%	50%			
Both primary and secondary production (i.e., the production of agricultural products/wood/fishery and/or aquaculture products) and the processing of these products and biowaste into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)		50%		50%	50%			
Only processing of bio-based materials into value added products (such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
Both processing of bio-based materials and biowaste into value-added products (such as food, feed, bio-products, and bioenergy)	50%		50%			50%	50%	
<p>* The corrections on the approximate number of interviewing end-users were made assuming that up to 50% of the business entities of secondary production (food, bio-based chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plastics, textile, bioenergy, etc.) operate in rural areas.</p> <p>** The corrections of the number of respondents according to bioeconomy sectors can be made (if necessary) by country partners (experts) who know the actual situation of the rural economy structure well in their own country. The corrections are recommended.</p> <p>*** Legal forms of enterprises in the sectors: food, beverage, tobacco; wood, wood products and furniture; forestry and logging; water systems; biomaterials/bioproducts; bioenergy</p> <p>**** Legal forms of farms/enterprises in agriculture sector</p>								

Table 27: Sampling frame for interviewing end-users for Romania

8 Annex II: Questionnaire for end-users

Objective of “BioRural”

BioRural’s main objective is creating a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.

Questionnaire focus

This questionnaire focuses on individuals or small to medium sized organisations, whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes (Food & Agriculture, Forestry & Natural Habitats, Water Systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials) and who mainly operate in rural areas, and their activities are limited to the interests of the primary and secondary sector.

The goal of this survey is to assess and evaluate the current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy and identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

As a result, we can contribute to the body of knowledge regarding innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions by providing an overview of end-user’s needs, ideas, and interests.

Instructions for end-users:

The interview is conducted using a participatory approach when the research respondent and researcher are filling out the questionnaire together.

The researcher introduces the purpose of the questionnaire and consults on a better understanding of definitions, and interpretation of survey questions (if needed). The respondents are asked to carefully read the question and mark their selected answer ✓, and/or to answer a question in a written/explanatory form.

This questionnaire can be filled out on a printed questionnaire form and/or e-document, filling it online.

The questionnaire consists of 31 questions which are divided into three main groups:

1. General information about the respondent (~20 min).
2. Barriers and driving factors to adopt bio-based solutions (~15 min).
3. Needs, ideas, and interests (~15 min).

It takes from 40 to 60 minutes to complete this questionnaire and discuss it with a researcher.

Privacy statement

Personal data will be completely anonymised and will not be sold to any third parties or shared with other actors/parties. The information collected in these surveys will be anonymised. No one will be able to trace results back to the individuals or small to medium sized organisations.

QUESTIONS

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Gender

Gender types	Mark your choice, ✓
Male	
Female	
Prefer not to say	

2. Age

Age categories	Mark your choice, ✓
Less than 25 years	
25-39 years	
40-49 years	
50-59 years	
60-74 years	
75 or over years	

3. Education

Education levels	Mark your choice, ✓
Basic (Primary education, Lower secondary education)	
Intermediate (Upper secondary education, post-secondary non-tertiary education)	
Advanced (Short-cycle tertiary education, Bachelor's or equivalent, Master's or equivalent, Doctorate of equivalent)	

4. Country: _____

5. Region (NUTS3) (specify the code and name) _____

6. What is the legal form of your farm/enterprise?

Legal form for farm* Legal form for enterprises**	Mark your choice, ✓
Natural person*	
Legal person*	
Group holding*	
Common land unit*	
Sole proprietorship**	
Partnership, co-operatives, associations**	
Limited liability enterprise**	

7. What is the size of your farm/enterprise?

Persons employed (hired workers and self-employed*)	Mark your choice, ✓
Less than 10 persons employed	
From 10 to 49 persons employed	
From 50 to 249 persons employed	

* owner-managers; partners engaged in a regular activity in the enterprise and deriving financial advantages from the enterprise

8. What is the experience of your farm/enterprise in the field of activity?

Years	Mark your choice, ✓
Less than 5 years	
5-10 years	
11-15 years	
16 -20 years	
More than 20 years	

9. What is your level of awareness about innovative small scale the bio-based solutions?

Self-assessment of the awareness	Give a score (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
I have sufficient knowledge of bio-based solutions*					

*bio-based solutions are innovative technologies and practices based on circularity that produce or utilise biomass sustainably as compared to mainstream practices that produce or utilise biomass without significant innovations or sustainable outputs

10. I am aware that the following items can be produced using biomaterials and/or bio-based products (derived from biomass, such as plants, trees, algae, or animals):

Awareness	Give a score to each item (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Agricultural products					
Forestry products and public greenery					
Fishing and aquaculture products					
Food and feed and its additives					
Catering products (disposable tableware, etc.)					
Wood, wood products, furniture					
Fibers and biotextiles					
Pulp and paper, paper products					
Packaging material (beverage bottles, food packaging, carrier bags, etc.)					
Cleaning biomaterials, personal care, and home care bio-products					
Biochemicals (lubricants, adhesives, industrial solvents, paints, and protective coatings, etc.)					
Bioenergy (solid biofuel, pellets, biodiesel, bioethanol, biogas, etc.)					
Compost, and bio-fertilizers					
Construction and building biomaterials (construction wood, insulations, etc.)					
Other, please specify:					

11. In which of 5 bioeconomy sectors you are operating (multiple choice)?

Bioeconomy sector / Themes ¹	Sub-sector/Sub-themes	Mark your choice, ✓
Food & Agriculture Food & Agriculture	Food processing	
	Animal feed processing	
	Livestock production	
	Greenhouses	
	Crops production	
	Organic waste management	
Forestry & Natural Habitats Forestry & Natural Habitats Forestry & Natural Habitats	Forestry and logging	
	Wood based industries	
Water Systems Water Systems Water Systems	Traditional water-based activities (aquaculture, fishing, etc.) in inland waters and/or at sea	
	Innovative water-based activities (algae production, etc.)	
Bioenergy Bioenergy Bioenergy	Solid biofuel	
	Liquid biofuels	
	Biogas	
	Bio-based heat	
	Bio-based electricity	
Biomaterials/Bio-based products Biomaterials/Bio-based products Biomaterials/Bio-based products	Producer of raw biomaterial (bioplastic pellets, bio-rubber, bio-colours, etc.)	
	Producer of consumer-ready biomaterial/bio-based products (bioplastic bottles, biocosmetics, textiles, paper, etc.)	
<i>Other (please comment if any):</i>		

Comment for interviewer: Please show/explain the “Examples of Biobased Solutions” to the end-user (Annex IV).

12. Are you adopting any bio-based solution?

- Yes
- No

QUESTIONS FOR ADOPTERS OF BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS

13. My innovative product/production process will continue to be relevant for society after 2030.

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

14. What type of bio-based solutions are you adopting? Please specify at least one choice and do not leave empty cells (write n/a if not applicable)

Types & Characteristics of Bio-based solutions	Short description (What is used for, output, etc.)
Bio-based product	

¹ The examples per Bioeconomy theme are provided in Annex IV.

<i>Bio-based product refers to products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees, or animals (the biomass can have undergone physical, chemical, or biological treatment)</i>	
Bio-based technology <i>Bio-based technology focuses on biobased technological applications during: degradation of by-products, waste, residues and production of valuable products or energy from renewable resource</i>	
Bio-based process <i>Bio-based processes mean switching to using biological resources and biological processing methods in a sustainable way</i>	
<i>Other, please specify:</i>	

15. What is the scale at which the bio-based solution operates? (Multiple choices)

- Farm/enterprises
- Village
- Community
- Specific industry in rural areas
- Other, please specify: _____

16. Have you had any engagement with any of the following stakeholders to understand if and how your bio-based solution could become more sustainable (regenerative, inclusive, circular), applicable, replicable, etc.

- **Yes, I had it with** (please highlight your choice, multiple choices):
 - Customers
 - Suppliers
 - Researchers
 - External advisors
 - Authority of legislator
 - Associations
 - Thematic networks
 - Public entities
 - Own employees
 - Other, please specify: _____
- **I did not have any engagement with any of the stakeholders mentioned above.**

17. If your answer is YES to question 16, please explain what the nature and purpose of the engagement and/or consultation was with the relevant stakeholders. Please comment: _____

18. What kind of incentives led you to become an adopter? (Multiple choice): _____

- Easy replicable good practice
- Positive legislative framework to switch to bio-based solution
- Government subsidies and/or other support schemes
- Enhanced product performance and/or functionalities
- Demand, public perceptions, and consumer behaviour on 'bio-based' alternatives and megatrends
- Competition with successful brand owners' companies that are already investing in bio-based alternatives
- Economic benefit
- Other, please specify: _____

QUESTIONS FOR NON-ADOPTERS OF BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS

19. What are the reasons why you are not adopting innovative bio-based solutions? Please comment.

20. What kind of information would you need before deciding to adopt any bio-based solution?

Information needed	Give a score to each item (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Demonstration					
Cost benefit model to reflect the bio-based activity specifics					
Peer-to-Peer conversations with adopter					
Consultation with official advisor (private or public)					
Personal test					
Other, please specify:					

21. Would you give it a try to begin adopting a bio-based solution if it were supported through subsidies?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

22. If your answer to 21 question is YES, which category of bio-based solution would you apply? (Multiple choice)

- **Bio-based product**
(Bio-based product refers to products wholly or partly derived from biomass, such as plants, trees, or animals (the biomass can have undergone physical, chemical, or biological treatment))
- **Bio-based technology**
(Bio-based technology focuses on biobased technological applications during degradation of by-products, waste, residues and production of valuable products or energy from renewable resource)
- **Bio-based process** (Bio-based processes mean switching to using biological resources and biological processing methods in a sustainable way)
- **Other (please specify):** _____

23. Would you adopt any bio-based solution if you could cooperate and share the costs with others?

- Yes
- No
- I am not sure

QUESTIONS FOR ADOPTERS & NON-ADOPTERS OF BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS

BARRIERS AND DRIVING FACTORS TO ADOPT BIO-BASED SOLUTIONS

24. Identify the barriers your farm/organization has/must overcome to adopt bio-based solutions.

Barriers to adopt bio-based solutions	<i>Give a score to each item</i> (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
1. Technical capacity					
2. Lack of knowledge					
3. Lack of financial capital					
4. Lack of partnerships					
5. Insufficient consumer interests/awareness					
6. Lack of clear guidelines or there is not a national bioeconomy strategy in action					
7. Uncertainty around environmental benefits					
8. Feedstock or ingredient supply uncertainties					
9. Incompatibility with existing processes (e.g., recycling schemes) or high replacement costs					
10. Higher life-cycle costs to buyers (from purchase to disposal)					
11. Legislative barriers					
Other, please specify:					

25. In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of customer demand for bio-based products?

The main barriers to growth of customer demand	<i>Give a score to each item</i> (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
1. Uncertainty regarding sustainability of bio-based products					
2. Surplus of on-the-market products					
3. Lack of customer knowledge on quality benefits of bio-based products					
4. Too high price of bio-based products					
5. Too small market to cover demand if it grows fast					
Other, please specify:					

26. What are the main driving factors for adoption of bio-based solutions?

Driving factors for adoption of bio-based solutions	Give a score to each item (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Supplier/Customer demand					
Meeting sustainability targets					
Regulatory framework/compliance					
Environmental reasons/ benefits/welfare					
Long-term economic benefits					
Diversification of operations					
Financial incentive: subsidy and/or tax exemption					
Being and innovator					
Technical reasons (functionality/ efficiency/ recyclability / biodegradability)					
Peer/community pressure					
Supporting a local/circular economy					
Competitiveness					
Other, please specify:					

NEEDS, IDEAS, AND INTERESTS

27. What are your specific needs when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solution?

Specific needs	Give a score to each item (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Superior quality of bio-based solutions in comparison to conventional solutions					
Cost-competitive products					
Compatible with existing processes					
Superior environmental performance (low negative impact)					
Use for locally sourced feedstocks					
Coverage of customers need for bio-based solutions					
Other, please specify:					

28. Does your farm or enterprise need support to identify opportunities for bio-based solutions?

- Yes
- No

29. If your answer to question 28 is YES, please specify what kind of support would you seek? (Multiple choice)

- Training

- Advisory
- Research
- Financial
- Other (please specify): _____

30. In your opinion/experience, what would be useful to speed up innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas?

Factors having potential to speed up innovative bio-based solutions	Give a score to each item (Scores: 5 – strongly agree; 4 – agree; 3 – I am not sure; 2 – disagree; 1 – strongly disagree)				
	5	4	3	2	1
Educational material and training on bio-based solutions					
Informative online resources, online portals, and networking platforms where information can be exchanged about bio-based solutions and their applications as well as information about producers					
Communications and informative events about bio-based solutions (media events, public discussions, etc.)					
Decision making process with the participation of the wider public (public consultations, etc.)					
Surveys and research about bio-based solutions					
Incentives for consumers to buy sustainable bio-based products and bioenergy products					
A clear certification and labelling regulation framework for bio-based products and packaging					
Advisory services and/or knowledge transfer systems for farmers to improve their understanding of the opportunities available to them in the production of bio-materials, bio-based products and bioenergy products					
Economic and regulative support for new bio-based industries and the greening of traditional industries`					
Legislation obliging the use of bio-based products and bioenergy products in applications which are proven to have environmental benefits					
Specialized agricultural exhibitions, Demo projects and showcases, cross visits (one-to-one and multiple)					
Peer-to-peer knowledge exchange					
Competitiveness in the market					
Incentives to producers to adopt bio-based solutions					
Other, please specify:					

31. If you are interested in being a part of BioRural ERBN* Please provide us with your contact details:

*European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) – a network of actors playing different roles for Bioeconomy expansion in rural areas.

Why to join Biorural ERBN? Locate, connect with network and existing projects, develop synergies with Bioeconomy individual actors from all over the Europe, gain the knowledge exchange, contribute towards and inclusive transition to a circular bio-based economy.

9 Annex III: Questionnaire for experts

Objective of “BioRural”

BioRural’s main objective is creating a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.

Questionnaire focus

This questionnaire focuses on experts in the bio-based sector, whose main profession and/or focus is within one or more of the five bioeconomy themes (Food & Agriculture, Forestry & Natural Habitats, Water Systems, Bioenergy, Biomaterials) operated in rural areas.

The goal of this survey is to assess and evaluate the current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy and identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas.

As a result, we can contribute to the body of knowledge regarding innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions by providing an overview of experts’ capacities, needs and interests.

Instructions for experts:

The interview is conducted using a participatory approach, when the research respondent and researcher are filling out the questionnaire together.

The researcher introduces the purpose of the questionnaire and consults on a better understanding of definitions, and interpretation of survey questions (if needed). The respondents are asked to carefully read the question and mark their selected answer ✓, and/or to answer a question in a written/explanatory form.

This questionnaire can be filled out on a printed questionnaire form and/or e-document, filling it online.

The questionnaire consists of 23 questions which are divided into three main groups:

1. General information (about the respondent) (~20 min).
2. Driving factors and barriers to adopt bio-based solutions (~15 min).
3. Needs, ideas, and interests (~15 min).

It takes from 40 to 60 minutes to complete this questionnaire and discuss it with a researcher.

Privacy statement

Personal data will be completely anonymised and will not be sold to any third parties or shared with other actors/parties. The information collected in these surveys will be anonymised. No one will be able to trace results back to the individuals or small to medium sized organisations.

GENERAL INFORMATION

INFORMATION ABOUT THE EXPERT

1. Country: _____

2. Gender

Gender types	Mark your choice, ✓
Male	
Female	
Prefer not to say	

3. Age

Age categories	Mark your choice, ✓
25-39 years	
40-49 years	
50-59 years	
60-74 years	
75 or over years	

4. Education

Education levels	Mark your choice, ✓
Bachelor's or equivalent	
Master's or equivalent	
Doctorate or equivalent	

5. What is your experience in the field of activity?

Years	Mark your choice, ✓
Less than 5 years	
5-10 years	
11-15 years	
16 -20 years	
More than 20 years	

6. What is your expertise in the field of circular bioeconomy and the adoption of bio-based solutions:

- I am a professor/ researcher performing with experimental research, consulting, and preparing scientific recommendations for better development and adoption of bio-based solutions
- I am policy maker/ developer of regional policy and funding schemes
- I am advisor/ Innovation broker consulting on development and adoption of bio-based solutions
- I am developer/ producer of bio-based solutions
- Other (please specify): _____

7. In which of 5 bioeconomy sectors you are operating as an expert? (Multiple choice)

Bioeconomy sector / Themes ²	Sub-sector /Sub-themes	Mark your choice, ✓
Food & Agriculture	Food processing	
	Livestock production	
	Greenhouses	
	Crops production	
	Organic waste management	
Forestry & Natural Habitats	Forestry and logging	
	Wood based industries	
Water Systems	Traditional water-based activities (aquaculture, fishing, etc.) in inland waters and / or at sea	
	Innovative water-based activities (algae production, etc.)	
Bioenergy	Solid Biofuel	
	Liquid Biofuels	
	Biogas	
	Bio-based heat	
	Bio-based electricity	
Biomaterials/Bio-based products	Producer of raw biomaterial (bioplastic pellets, bio-rubber, bio-colours, etc.)	
	Producer of consumer-ready biomaterial/bio-based products (bioplastic bottles, biocosmetics, textiles, paper, etc.)	
<i>Other (please comment if any):</i>		

DRIVING FACTORS AND BARRIERS

Please share your expertise on the following questions:

8. What is your opinion about the **current situation of the rural bioeconomy**? Why is the circular bioeconomy situation so different in the rural regions?
9. What kind of **incentives** (not only economic) are needed so that both the circular bioeconomy and innovative bio-based solutions in rural areas are easier and more often developed and applied?
10. What is your expert opinion, about the **sufficiently and efficiency of current policy** in rural regions to support the development and adoption of bio-based solutions?
11. What are the main **driving factors** of rural small scale produces, SMEs to adopt and/or develop bio-based solutions?
12. What are the main **barriers for adopters** to develop the bio-based solutions?
13. What are the **barriers for non-adopters** to adopt and develop the bio-based solutions?
14. **In your opinion/experience, what factors are the main barriers to growth of demand for biomaterials, bio-based products, and bioenergy products?**

² The examples per Bioeconomy theme are provided in Annex IV.

- 15. What is your opinion, does the **membership with small producer's groups/ cooperatives**, etc., are helping better to overcome the challenges that are facing adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions?
- 16. What **capacities** are needed to adopt and/or develop bio-based solutions in rural regions?
- 17. Do you think the **advisory/ brokerage services** are well developed to support adopters and non-adopters of bio-based solutions? To your opinion, what kind of advice they need the most?

NEEDS AND INTERESTS

- 18. Which type of **stakeholders** could influence small scale producers to convert to bio-based production/processing?
- 19. What are the specific **needs** when it comes to choosing an alternative innovative small-scale bio-based solutions?
- 20. Do you think that the **knowledge transfer system**, the share of experience and replicability of innovative bio-based solutions are efficient and integrated (e.g., involving different types of stakeholders depending on their functional performance), etc.?
- 21. What **information** is necessary to know about the bio-based solutions (for adopters and non-adopters)?
- 22. **What should be done to increase** the rural circular bioeconomy and better adoption of bio-based solutions in rural areas in a short and in a long time?
- 23. **If you are interested in being a part of BioRural ERBN*** Please provide us with your contact details):

*European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) – a network of actors playing different roles for Bioeconomy expansion in rural areas.

Why to join BioRural ERBN? Locate, connect with network and existing projects, develop synergies with Bioeconomy individual actors from all over the Europe, gain the knowledge exchange, contribute towards and inclusive transition to a circular bio-based economy.

OTHER COMMENTS AND IDEAS

Please list the additional comments and ideas which naturally raised during the survey:

10 Annex IV: Examples of bio-based solutions

Examples of Bio-based solutions per Bioeconomy theme

Bio-based solutions are innovative technologies and practices based on circularity that produce or utilise biomass sustainably as compared to mainstream practices that produce or utilise biomass without significant innovations or sustainable outputs.

For the **production** of raw biomass/feedstocks, we consider sustainable practices and technologies to be biobased solutions. For the **processing** of biomass/feedstocks, we consider sustainable technologies, processes and end products to be biobased solutions. This distinction exists as in the production of biobased feedstocks it is generally the process and technologies used in the production of the feedstock that determines its level of sustainability/circularity. For processed and finished products, it's a combination of efficient production systems (efficient technologies and processes) and the production of a sustainable bio end-product that distinguishes it from mainstream/traditional processing practices.

Please use the following descriptions and examples to determine whether you use/have adopted these types of technologies or practices. The examples provided below are indicative, an adopter may use other or additional relevant solutions.

For bioeconomy themes 1-3, a key guiding question is: "Do you adopt the following or similar practices and/or technologies in your operations?"

For bioeconomy themes 4-5, a key guiding question is: "Do you develop a sustainable product or use especially efficient technologies or practices in the production/processing process?"

Positive answer means that the user adopts bio-based solutions.

Theme	Sub-category	Examples of bio-based solutions (practices and technologies)
#1 Food & Agriculture	Crop production/open Field agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of conservation agriculture principles • Use of Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (e.g., Agri-PV, electric/biomethane tractors, no-till machinery) • Use of Smart agriculture principles/technologies
	Livestock production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use/production of RES on site (heat pumps, biogas, biomethane), smart control systems, energy efficient technologies
	Greenhouse production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat pumps, smart control systems
	Food/agro-processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% RES source, high energy efficient technologies in production process, Green packaging

Conservation Agriculture

Agri-PV

No-tiller

Smart Agriculture

Smart livestock control systems

Heat Pumps

Biogas

Smart Greenhouse control systems

Renewable Energy in food industry

Energy Efficiency solutions in food industry

WHAT MAKES A PACKAGE SUSTAINABLE?

Green Packaging

Theme	Sub-category	Examples of bio-based solutions (practices and technologies)
#2 Forestry & Natural Habitats	Forestry and logging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable forestry management • Sustainable logging practices (including replanting, selective logging and thinning, pruning). • Efficient implements
	Wood based industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood based industries that use wood waste • 100% RES source, high energy efficient technologies in production process

Swedish logging practices

Solar electric sawmill

Solar wood dryer

Thinning / selective logging

Replating-foresteing

Uses of wood waste

Theme	Sub-category	Examples of bio-based solutions (practices and technologies)
#3 Water Systems	Traditional water-based activities in inland waters and / or at sea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable aquaculture (organic principles) Implementing sustainable fishing practices
	Innovative water-based activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative algae production system, aquaponics 100% RES source, high energy efficient technologies in production process

Example of circular aquaculture

Algae production system

Aquaponics

Sustainable fishing practices

Renewable Energy in algae production

Theme	Sub-category	Examples of bio-based solutions (processes, technologies and products)
#4 Bioenergy	Solid and liquid biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High efficiency boilers Biomass Combined Heat and Power (CHP)
	Biogas and biomethane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biogas from sustainable feedstocks Biogas CHP Biomethane upgrading

High Efficient Boilers

Biogas from sustainable feedstocks

Biomass CHP

Biogas CHP

Biogas upgrading to Biomethane

Theme	Sub-category	Examples of bio-based solutions (processes, technologies and products)
#5 Biomaterials	Producer of raw biomaterial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioplastic pellets, biobased chemicals bio-rubber. Bio-colours, biochar • 100% RES source, high energy efficient technologies in production process
	Producer of consumer ready biomaterial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioplastic bottles, bio-cosmetics • 100% RES source, high energy efficient technologies in production process

Bioplastic pellet

Biochar

Bioplastic bottle

Bioplastic application

Biocomposite pellets

Wheat Bioplastics